

FROM ACCURACY TO INTERPRETABILITY IN AUTISM SCREENING

A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF MACHINE LEARNING
MODELS ON SYNTHETIC AUTISM DATA

KONSTANTINA LAMPROPOULOU

THESIS SUBMITTED IN PARTIAL FULFILLMENT
OF THE REQUIREMENTS FOR THE DEGREE OF
MASTER OF SCIENCE IN DATA SCIENCE & SOCIETY
AT THE SCHOOL OF HUMANITIES AND DIGITAL SCIENCES
OF TILBURG UNIVERSITY

STUDENT NUMBER

2121963

COMMITTEE

Dr. Gonzalo Nápoles

Dr. Marijn van Wingerden

LOCATION

Tilburg University

School of Humanities and Digital Sciences

Department of Cognitive Science &

Artificial Intelligence

Tilburg, The Netherlands

DATE

June 23th, 2025

WORD COUNT

8785

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

I would like to sincerely thank my thesis supervisor, Dr. Gonzalo Nápoles, for his unwavering support, expert guidance, and thoughtful feedback throughout this project. His insights and dedication greatly contributed to the quality and direction of this work. I am also grateful to Dr. Marijn van Wingerden for serving as the second reader and for his valuable time and comments. Lastly, I extend my heartfelt thanks to my family for their constant encouragement and support throughout this journey.

FROM ACCURACY TO INTERPRETABILITY IN AUTISM SCREENING

A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF MACHINE LEARNING MODELS
ON SYNTHETIC AUTISM DATA

KONSTANTINA LAMPROPOULOU

Abstract

Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) is a complex and increasingly prevalent neurodevelopmental condition that highlights the need for diagnostic tools that are both accurate and interpretable. While machine learning (ML) holds promise for ASD screening, limited transparency hinders clinical adoption. This thesis evaluates five ML classifiers—Logistic Regression (LR), Random Forest (RF), Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost), TabNet, and Long-Term Cognitive Networks (LTCNs)—on a synthetic ASD dataset under both imbalanced and Synthetic Minority Over-sampling Technique (SMOTE)-balanced conditions. Across models, standard metrics such as ROC-AUC, Weighted F1-score, precision-recall, and Cohen’s Kappa remained stable under balancing, with F1-scores between 0.85–0.91 and ROC-AUCs from 0.84–0.93. To assess interpretability, various feature attribution methods were compared. Native model importances capture internal feature rankings. Permutation Feature Importance (PFI) measures performance drops when feature values are shuffled. Shapley Additive Explanations (SHAP) apply game theory to assign fair contributions to each feature. Performance Marginalization Contribution (PMC) quantifies accuracy changes when a feature is removed. Faithfulness of explanations was evaluated with Performance Marginalization Curves (PMCs), where smaller area under the curve indicates closer alignment with model behavior. Additionally, Sparseness-Optimized Feature Importance (SOFI) was utilized which leverages PMCs to select a minimal yet relevant feature set, yielding interpretations that are compact and consistent. By emphasizing interpretability, this work examines how ML-based ASD screening can lead toward tools that clinicians can understand, patients can trust, and families can rely on-supporting more transparent, and informed care.

CONTENTS

1	Data Source, Ethics, Code, and Technology Statement	4
2	Introduction	4
2.1	Project Definition	5
2.2	Societal Relevance	5
2.3	Scientific Relevance	6
3	Research Strategy and Questions	6
3.1	Findings	8
4	Literature Review	8
4.1	Traditional ML Models in ASD Diagnosis	8
4.2	Deep Learning Models for ASD Screening	8
4.3	Hybrid and Fuzzy Systems	9
4.4	Attention-Based and Transformer Models	9
4.5	Explainability in Clinical ML	9
4.6	Real-World Applications of Interpretable ML	10
4.7	Summary and Research Gap	10
5	Methodology	11
5.1	Dataset Description	11
5.2	Data Cleaning and Preprocessing	12
5.3	Exploratory Data Analysis	12
5.4	Interpretation and Implications	16
5.5	Model Selection	17
6	Model Tuning and Evaluation Protocol	18
6.1	Explainability Techniques and Attribution Strategies	19
6.2	Marginalization Curves and SOFI	19
7	Results and Comparative Evaluation	19
7.1	Model Generalization, Robustness, and Comparative Insights	20
7.2	Gender Evaluation	21
8	Feature Importance Analysis (with SMOTE)	22
8.1	Feature Attribution Analysis	22
8.2	Model-Specific Observations	22
9	Performance Marginalization Curves with SMOTE	29
10	Evaluation Without SMOTE Oversampling	30
10.1	Performance Comparison	30
11	Feature Importance Analysis (Without SMOTE)	31
12	Performance Marginalization Curves Without SMOTE	39
13	Discussion	40
13.1	Answers to Research Questions	40
13.2	Emphasizing Societal and Scientific Impact	43

13.3	Limitations	43
13.4	Future Work	44
14	Conclusion	45
15	Appendix	51
15.1	Additional Demographic and Clinical Plots	51
15.2	Model Hyperparameter Grids	55
15.2.1	Summary of Key Findings in the Literature	55
15.3	Supplementary Evaluation Visuals with SMOTE	56
15.3.1	Best Hyperparameters with SMOTE	60
15.3.2	Precision–Recall Curves for Model Evaluation	61
15.3.3	Positive Prediction Rate (PPR) with SMOTE	63
15.3.4	Gender Distribution	64
15.4	Visual Diagnostics in the absence of SMOTE	68
15.4.1	Positive Prediction Rate without SMOTE	75
16	Gender-Specific Evaluation of Classification Models	75
16.1	Visual Inspection of Marginalization Curves	78
16.2	PMCs without SMOTE	81
16.3	Cross-Validation Performance Across Models	83
16.4	Glossary of Terms	84
16.5	Robustness Evaluation under Gaussian Noise Injection	84
16.6	SVD-Based Initialization and Uniform Feature Influence	86
16.7	Python libraries and packages	87
17	AQ-10 Adult Autism Spectrum Quotient Questionnaire	88

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1	Model Performance Summary	21
Table 2	Performance Evaluation Using Kappa Score	21
Table 3	AUC Scores of Feature Marginalization Curves	30
Table 4	Model performance summary without SMOTE	31
Table 5	AUC Scores of Feature Marginalization Curves	40
Table 6	Hyperparameter grid used for model optimization.	55
Table 7	ML Models for ASD Diagnosis.	55
Table 8	Summary of Selected ML Studies in ASD Diagnosis	56
Table 9	Best Hyperparameters for Each Model	60
Table 10	Positive Prediction Rates by Gender	63
Table 11	Best Hyperparameters Without SMOTE	68
Table 12	Test F1 Scores With and Without SMOTE	71
Table 13	Comparison of Kappa Scores With and Without SMOTE	71

Table 14	Train and Validation F1 Scores With and Without SMOTE	72
Table 15	Positive Prediction Rates by Gender without SMOTE Balancing	75
Table 16	Diagnostic performance (Precision, Recall, F1-score) by model and gender, with and without SMOTE (ASD class).	76
Table 17	Model performance under Gaussian noise injection (training data)	85
Table 18	Overview of Python libraries and packages used	87

1 DATA SOURCE, ETHICS, CODE, AND TECHNOLOGY STATEMENT

The dataset used in this thesis is publicly available on Kaggle, sourced from the “Autism Spectrum Disorder Prediction” repository (Geb, 2022). It comprises synthetic data generated using Conditional Tabular GANs (CTGAN) from the Autism Screening for Adults dataset by Andrew M. (Kaggle, 2021). The dataset and competition were created by Suryansu Dash and Laxman Naik under the Google Developer Student Clubs at CET-Bhubaneswar. No real human or animal data was collected, and all entries are synthetic, ensuring anonymity. Data and code ownership remain with the original authors. All figures and visualizations were created by the author. Software tools are listed in Appendix, and the full implementation is available on the project’s [GitHub repository](#). ChatGPT (OpenAI, 2021) was used for language refinement, and Grammarly (Grammarly Inc., 2023) for grammar checking. No AI tools contributed to idea generation or content creation. The typesetting was done entirely using Texmarker.

2 INTRODUCTION

ASD is a complex neurodevelopmental condition marked by persistent social communication deficits and restricted, repetitive behaviors. Its heterogeneous nature often leads to delayed or missed diagnoses. As of 2022, 1 in 31 children in the United States had received an ASD diagnosis (Shaw et al., 2025), highlighting both a rise in prevalence and growing pressure on healthcare systems. Early diagnosis is associated with improved cognitive, social, and behavioral outcomes (Okoye et al., 2023). However, current procedures are often time-consuming and subjective. Standard tools like ADOS-2 and CARS-2 rely on structured observation and caregiver input (Huang et al., 2023; Lord et al., 2018). Although their validity, these tools require consistent engagement and instruction-following, which may exclude individuals with more severe or non-compliant ASD profiles (Huang

et al., 2023). ML models offer promise for ASD screening by identifying complex patterns in behavioral and demographic data (Duda et al., 2016; Thabtah, 2019). In medical contexts, particularly developmental assessment, transparency is essential, while early screening depends on subtle behavioral cues with long-term implications (Doshi-Velez & Kim, 2017; Holzinger et al., 2019). Interpretable models like LR provide transparency but may lack performance, while more complex models such as ensembles or neural networks offer greater accuracy at the expense of explainability (Balcan & Sharma, 2025; Yang et al., 2022). This trade-off is a central challenge in medical Artificial Intelligence AI, where both accuracy and interpretability are critical (Vellido, 2019). This thesis compares five ML classifiers by predictive performance and interpretability. It introduces a quantitative framework combining performance metrics, feature importance, and marginalization curves to evaluate alignment between model behavior and explanations, aiming to support clinically explainable and socially responsible AI for ASD screening.

2.1 *Project Definition*

This thesis investigates how interpretability can be integrated into ML models for ASD screening, with the goal of balancing high predictive accuracy and meaningful explainability. A comparative evaluation framework is developed with five models—LR, RF, XGBoost, TabNet, and LTCNs—under balanced, imbalanced and noisy data conditions. The study analyzes how models respond to these scenarios to assess robustness and consistency under realistic clinical constraints. LR serves as our baseline, providing a reference for evaluating the added complexity and trade-offs in more advanced architectures. We utilize different feature important attributions, PFI, SHAP, PMC, and native, offering insights into both intrinsic and post-hoc explanation methods. The reliability of these approaches, including SOFI but excluding PMC, is assessed using PMCs, which measure performance loss as top-ranked features are sequentially neutralized. The study aims to provide a reproducible methodology for building diagnostic models that are not only accurate, but also ethically aligned—defined here as transparent, and accountable within clinical decision-making contexts.

2.2 *Societal Relevance*

The global rise in ASD prevalence places increasing pressure on healthcare systems, particularly in regions with limited access to specialized services. This burden extends to families, many of whom lack the resources and knowledge to navigate associated challenges (Babalola et al., 2024).

Diagnostic delays and inconsistencies remain common, often compounding long-term difficulties (Okoye et al., 2023). Interpretable models can reduce diagnostic uncertainty, promote consistency across practitioners, and improve communication with families. When based on structured questionnaires—as in this study—models become lightweight, infrastructure-independent, and suitable for mobile or community-based use. Unlike neuroimaging tools requiring costly equipment (Cortese et al., 2025), these models are scalable and globally accessible. Structured inputs also enable subgroup and fairness-aware analyses, supporting more equitable access to early intervention (Portillo et al., 2024) and advancing broader goals of social equity and neurodiversity inclusion.

2.3 *Scientific Relevance*

While prior research in ASD classification using ML has primarily focused on accuracy, there is a growing shift toward models that provide faithful and clinically interpretable explanations (Vellido, 2019). This work contributes to the advancing field of interpretable AI in healthcare and introduces an integrated framework that jointly evaluates model performance and explanatory value. Its novelty lies in combining standard classification metrics with a systematic assessment of interpretability, grounded in both ML theory and clinical relevance. By comparing model-specific and model-agnostic attribution methods across diverse model architectures and data conditions and evaluating them through PMCs, the study identifies which approaches yield the most stable and meaningful explanations. Advancing responsible feature attribution brings us closer to a form of explainability that clinicians can trust and families can understand that supports the development of more humane, and equitable diagnostic tools for ASD.

3 RESEARCH STRATEGY AND QUESTIONS

The research design is structured around one main research question and three sub-questions, each addressing a distinct layer of the accuracy–interpretability trade-off.

Main Research Question (RQ1): *How do ML models perform in the classification of Autism Spectrum Disorder?*

This thesis examines the performance of ML models in classification problems such as autism screening, emphasizing not only on the predictive accuracy but also on the interpretability and trustworthiness of their outputs. We utilize a range of algorithms from inherently transparent to more opaque models, which are evaluated to understand how they influence decision quality and explanation reliability. The objective is to assess

how different models and attribution techniques effect trustworthiness in sensitive diagnostic tasks.

Sub-question 1 (RQ2): *How do different ML models for ASD classification perform in terms of predictive accuracy, as measured by F1-score, AUC, and Cohen's Kappa?*

This question assesses the raw classification performance, including white-box models such as LR, to semi-transparent grey-box models such as TabNet and TabNet and fully opaque black-box models such as RF and XGBoost. We emphasize on weighted F1 in order to ensure balanced consideration of precision and recall, while AUC and Cohen's Kappa provide complementary insights into discriminative power and agreement beyond chance. All models are evaluated under consistent preprocessing and both imbalanced and SMOTE-balanced conditions.

Sub-question 2 (RQ3): *To what extent do model-specific and model-agnostic feature importance methods agree across interpretable, quasi-interpretable, and black-box models, in terms of feature prioritization?*

This question identifies the alignment between model-agnostic methods and model-specific methods. Each model reveals its importance in different ways-for example, LR via model coefficients and LTCNs through learned weights-and prioritize different features. We explore different attribution methods such as PFI, PMC, SHAP in terms of consistency and their alignment with native feature importance, which together capture the trustworthiness of each model. The goal is to evaluate whether post-hoc explanations reflect the model's internal reasoning.

Sub-question 3 (RQ4): *Which feature importance method report the most accurate explanations, as measured by the performance-marginalization curve?*

To evaluate how model performance degrades as top-ranked features are progressively neutralized, we apply PMCs. From these curves, we compute the area under the curve (AUC), which serves as a quantitative measure of the strength and fidelity of each explanation method. Several feature importance techniques are considered in this analysis, native, SHAP, PFI, and SOFI. Unlike traditional methods that rely on perturbation or surrogate modeling, SOFI directly optimizes the PMCs itself. This approach allows for a rigorous comparative evaluation of how well each method captures the underlying decision logic of the model.

An additional objective of this thesis is to explore whether model predictions are consistent across demographic subgroups (e.g., gender), in order to assess fairness and support trustworthy deployment. Together, these questions offer a comprehensive lens through which to assess ML models for ASD screening, addressing both their diagnostic accuracy and the quality of their decision support.

3.1 Findings

Complex models like XGBoost and RF outperformed simpler ones like LR, though performance differences were modest. Feature importance analysis, validated via PMCs, showed XGBoost consistently prioritized similar features across attribution methods, indicating stability. Among explanation techniques, SOFI was most effective in identifying meaningful features. These results suggest that XGBoost, paired with robust attribution methods like SOFI, offers a reliable foundation for developing trustworthy diagnostic tools for autism screening.

4 LITERATURE REVIEW

Note: Unless otherwise specified, the terms “interpretable ML,” “explainable AI (XAI),” and “transparent models” are used interchangeably throughout this thesis.

4.1 Traditional ML Models in ASD Diagnosis

LR, Decision Trees (DTs), and RF are widely used in ASD classification due to their simplicity and interpretability. Thabtah (2019) highlighted their use in behavioral screening tools but noted performance issues due to class imbalance and the absence of feature relevance analysis. Duda et al. (2016) applied LR and RF to the Social Responsiveness Scale (SRS) dataset with 2,925 individuals, reporting a high AUC of 0.965 for LR using only five features selected via mutual information. Tree-based models like RF required more features for comparable accuracy. However, DTs are prone to overfitting—especially on small or imbalanced datasets, and may become computationally expensive as tree depth increases. RF mitigate overfitting by aggregating multiple trees, however this ensemble structure reduces interpretability (Halabaku & Bytyçi, 2024). In contrast, while LR offers high interpretability, it assumes linear relationships between features and outcomes (Labhade-Kumar, 2024).

4.2 Deep Learning Models for ASD Screening

Deep learning models can capture complex non-linear patterns in high-dimensional data. Heinsfeld et al. (2017) used stacked autoencoders with a multilayer perceptron on fMRI data from the ABIDE dataset, achieving 70% accuracy. Tang et al. (2020) employed a multimodal CNN integrated voxel-level features with ROI variables, reaching 74% accuracy and 95% recall and F1-score 0.805. Mukherjee et al. (2024) reported 97% accuracy

using LSTMs on narrative clinical reports. However, deep learning models require substantial computational resources and are highly sensitive to data preprocessing, which can affect their robustness and reproducibility in clinical applications (Javed et al., 2025).

4.3 *Hybrid and Fuzzy Systems*

Hybrid models that combine fuzzy logic, neural networks, and attention mechanisms aim to balance interpretability and performance. The AT-STTSK model, proposed by Zhang et al. (2024), is a fuzzy TSK model enhanced with Transformers, achieving 85.7% accuracy on ABIDE rs-fMRI data. Szwed (2021) introduced Fuzzy Cognitive Maps (FCMs), which match traditional models' performance but lack interpretability metrics; their experiments were limited to small datasets, raising concerns about scalability. Alqaysi et al. (2024) benchmarked 72 hybrid models using 2-tuple linguistic neutrosophic fuzzy sets and identified SFS/LR-DTs as the top performer, but the study does not assess interpretability or discuss the computational cost of large-scale benchmarking.

4.4 *Attention-Based and Transformer Models*

TabNet, an attention-based model for tabular data, offers native interpretability via sequential feature masking (Arik & Pfister, 2021). However, Mainas et al. (2024) reported weak performance on neuroimaging-based ASD tasks, with AUC and F1-scores consistently below 0.70, while SVMs outperformed it. In contrast, Liu et al. (2025) introduced a deep learning framework combining attention with LSTM to model dynamic functional connectivity in ASD using rs-fMRI data from the ABIDE dataset. Their model achieved 74.9% accuracy and 75.5% precision under intra-site cross-validation which is comparable to SVM, RF, and standard LSTM—while emphasizing the importance of temporal patterns in ASD detection.

4.5 *Explainability in Clinical ML*

Integrating behavioral, imaging, and genetic data has shown potential in improving diagnostic accuracy. Cheong et al. (2024) combined methylation profiles, thalamocortical connectivity, and behavioral features in an XG-Boost classifier, reaching 83.95% accuracy. While SHAP (Lundberg & Lee, 2017) offers a consistent framework for interpreting such models, however its application can lead to instability and misleading insights (Hung & Marques-Silva, 2024). Post-hoc explanation methods like SHAP and LIME

are widely applied in ASD research. For instance, Bokka et al. (2024) identified prenatal ASD risk factors, while Alves et al. (2023) used SHAP on fMRI data (500 subjects, 242 with ASD) to interpret functional connectivity differences, highlighting regions such as the left ventral posterior cingulate cortex and the cerebellum as less connected in ASD. However, their study lacked validation of SHAP explanations, raising concerns about reliability—an issue emphasized by Tonekaboni et al. (2019). Additionally, den Broeck et al. (2021) show that even under simplified assumptions, computing SHAP values can be as hard as computing model expectations, making it computationally intractable for common models like LR.

4.6 *Real-World Applications of Interpretable ML*

Recent advances highlight the real-world potential of interpretable ML in autism screening. The *SenseToKnow* app, used during pediatric visits, achieved an AUC of 0.90 with 87.8% sensitivity and 97.8% NPV, while maintaining stable performance across sex and ethnicity. Using SHAP, the app provides explanations based on behaviors like gaze and facial expression, increasing trust and transparency. Combined with M-CHAT-R/F, it improved PPV from 14.6% to 63.4%, demonstrating how interpretable ML can enhance early detection and reduce diagnostic disparities. However, further validation is needed in more diverse and independent populations, as the current sample may include selection and prevalence biases (Perochon et al., 2023).

As summarized in [Appendix Tables 7 and 8](#), existing ASD models vary in interpretability, performance, and explainability integration.

4.7 *Summary and Research Gap*

Although a wide array of ML models have achieved strong classification results for ASD, few have evaluated explainability under different data conditions 7. The trade-off between performance and interpretability remains underexplored (Bell et al., 2022), and there is a pressing need to shift toward more explainable models—while simultaneously validating the reliability of their explanations (Vimbi et al., 2025). Additionally, prior analyses using the Kaggle ASD dataset often rely on simple classification methods, with little attention to feature attribution or the validation of model explanations.

This thesis addresses critical gaps in current ASD diagnostic research by evaluating five ML classifiers under different conditions. It integrates multiple interpretability methods to assess model behavior and uses PMCs to quantify the faithfulness of the resulting explanations. Furthermore, it

applies the SOFI method, which not only leverages marginalization curves for evaluation but also incorporates them directly into its optimization objective to produce more reliable and sparse feature importance rankings. By addressing this research gap, the work aims to improve trust in ML-driven healthcare tools, promote earlier diagnosis, and help reduce stigma, especially the kind that may arise from misleading or unfaithful feature importance explanations.

5 METHODOLOGY

5.1 Dataset Description

The dataset used in this study is a synthetic version of the Autism Screening for Adults dataset, generated using Conditional Tabular Generative Adversarial Networks (CTGAN). Created by Suryansu Dash and Laxman Naik, the synthetic data preserves the statistical properties of the original while ensuring complete participant anonymity (Geb, 2022).

The dataset comprises 800 anonymized questionnaire responses related to ASD. The binary target variable, *Class/ASD*, denotes diagnostic classification, where 1 represents ASD-positive and 0 indicates neurotypical status.

¹ Although synthetic, the dataset preserves key statistical patterns, making it a valid proxy for benchmarking interpretability techniques.

- **Behavioral Indicators:** Ten binary variables (*A1–A10*) derived from DSM-5 screening questions.
- **Psychometric Score:** A continuous variable, *result*, representing the total screening score.
- **Demographic and Clinical Features:** Age, gender, ethnicity, country of residence, relationship to the subject (*relation*), prior app usage (*used_app_before*), history of neonatal jaundice (*jaundice*), and family history of autism (*austim*).

The dataset was split using stratified sampling into 80% training (640 samples) and 20% testing (160 samples), preserving the original class distribution. All preprocessing steps were applied exclusively to the training set to avoid data leakage.

¹ The term *neurotypical* refers to individuals who do not meet diagnostic criteria for autism or other neurodevelopmental conditions. It is used here to distinguish from autistic individuals in a neutral, non-pathologizing way.

5.2 Data Cleaning and Preprocessing

The dataset was preprocessed to ensure consistency, and compatibility with ML algorithms. The following steps were applied:

- **String Normalization:** Categorical values in *ethnicity* and *relation* were converted to lowercase and stripped of leading/trailing whitespace.
- **Missing Value Imputation:** Non-informative placeholders such as '?' were treated as missing values and imputed using the most frequent category (mode) within each variable.
- **Encoding:**
 - Binary variables were encoded as follows: *gender* ($f = 0, m = 1$), *used_app_before*, *jaundice*, and *austim* ($no = 0, yes = 1$).
 - Multicategorical variables—*ethnicity*, *relation*, and *contry_of_res*²—were transformed via label encoding.
- **Feature Removal:** The variable *age_desc* was dropped due to redundancy and lack of variability.

After preprocessing, the dataset was fully numeric and free of missing values. The resulting feature matrix is denoted as X_{full} , and the target variable as y_{full} .

5.3 Exploratory Data Analysis

Exploratory Data Analysis (EDA) was conducted to examine class imbalance, feature relevance, demographic skews, and potential confounding variables. These insights informed model selection, validation strategies, and interpretability evaluation.

- **Class Imbalance:** The ASD-positive class constituted a minority of samples, as shown in Figure 1, necessitating stratified sampling during the train-test split and the use of SMOTE for training. This imbalance risks biased learning, where models may favor the majority class and underperform in detecting ASD-positive cases—an outcome with significant clinical consequences. Therefore, applying SMOTE is essential not only for improving the F1-score but also for ensuring fair treatment of the minority class.

² The original variable name *contry_of_res* is retained to maintain consistency with the dataset, despite the spelling error.

Figure 1: Class distribution of ASD and neurotypical cases. The plot highlights the significant underrepresentation of ASD-positive samples.

Figure 2: Two-dimensional PCA projection of behavioral and psychometric features, colored by ASD diagnosis. The projection reveals partial class separation, suggesting structure in the feature space relevant for classification.

The PCA projection (Figure 2) shows that the feature space has meaningful structure and some class separation. This suggests the applicability of using ML classifiers, but the observed overlap emphasizes the need for strong interpretability tools, as decision boundaries may not be easily interpretable in higher dimensions.

- **Distribution Analysis:** The psychometric score distribution (Figure 3) and behavioral indicators (Figure 4) show higher values among ASD-

positive individuals. These patterns align with known clinical markers and support the predictive value of DSM-based questionnaire items.

Figure 3: Distribution of psychometric scores across ASD and neurotypical groups. The density plot exhibits a rightward shift in the ASD group, indicating elevated screening scores.

Figure 4: Frequencies of positive responses to behavioral indicators, stratified by ASD diagnosis. ASD-positive individuals exhibit systematically higher prevalence of affirmative responses.

The psychometric and behavioral features not only demonstrate strong separation but also clinical coherence, confirming that these variables

capture relevant ASD traits. Their central role in the feature set justifies their prioritization in model development and interpretability evaluation.

- **Correlation Analysis:** The heatmap in Figure 5 reveals strong inter-correlations among behavioral indicators. Such multicollinearity can distort interpretability—particularly in linear models—and inflate or suppress attribution estimates in post-hoc techniques such as PFI.

Figure 5: The correlation heatmap (Pearson) shows numeric and binary behavioral indicators. While used for visual consistency, caution is needed in interpreting binary relationships, as strong correlations may indicate multicollinearity, affecting model attribution.

To mitigate attribution bias from redundancy, more robust attribution techniques—such as SHAP and SOFI—are used in later stages. Their ability to account for interaction effects and redundancy is crucial for valid feature importance interpretation.

- **Demographic and Clinical Trends:** Figures 24 and 30 show subgroup disparities that may affect model fairness and generalizability. Additional demographic plots, including age, ethnicity, relation to respondent, and prior app use, are provided in Appendix 15.1.

5.4 *Interpretation and Implications*

The EDA reveals meaningful structure in the data, supporting the viability of ML-based ASD screening. Strong effect sizes and well-separated feature distributions suggest that core behavioral and psychometric indicators provide clinically relevant signals. However, high multicollinearity, demographic skew, and proxy variables raise interpretability and fairness concerns. These findings motivate the study's emphasis on robust attribution methods and subgroup performance evaluation. EDA informs both methodological decisions and the ethical framing of the models developed in this work.

Figure 6: Overview of the ML pipeline applied to synthetic ASD data. The process includes data cleaning, exploratory analysis, and an 80/20 stratified train-test split. A suite of models—spanning black-box (XGBoost, RF), grey-box (TabNet, LTCNs), and white-box (LR)—is trained and optimized using grid search. Evaluation metrics include weighted F1-score and Cohen’s Kappa to account for class imbalance. Interpretability is assessed using SHAP, PMCs curves, PFI, SOFI, and native explainability tools tailored to each model type.

5.5 Model Selection

Classical interpretable models like **LR** and **RF** are included due to their simplicity and effectiveness. LR offers straightforward coefficient-based

explanations, while RF captures non-linear interactions via ensemble learning. More complex models such as **XGBoost** and **TabNet** expand this range. XGBoost is a high-performance framework using sequential, regularized decision trees to minimize prediction error, with features like parallelism, missing value handling, and post hoc interpretability tools such as feature importance and tree visualizations (Chen & Guestrin, 2016). TabNet introduces a novel approach to deep learning on tabular data using sequential attention and sparse feature selection, enabling both local and global interpretability; however, it requires heavy tuning and significant computational resources, which may limit its clinical scalability (Arik & Pfister, 2021). Additionally, LTCNs are assessed as a grey-box alternative. LTCNs replace traditional hidden layers with a recurrently connected input layer where each neuron maps directly to a domain-relevant feature or class. Through iterative activation updates, LTCNs converge on transparent predictions that make conceptual relationships explicitly traceable (Nápoles et al., 2021). This spectrum—from transparent statistical models to interpretable neural architectures—supports a comprehensive comparison of how modern ML tools can reconcile accuracy with the transparency required in high-stakes, real-world ASD screening contexts.

6 MODEL TUNING AND EVALUATION PROTOCOL

To ensure fair comparison and optimal performance, a unified hyperparameter optimization framework was adopted. All models underwent stratified 10-fold cross-validation with *GridSearchCV* to identify optimal settings and evaluate generalization. Initial 5-fold experiments yielded less stable outcomes, especially for black-box models like XGBoost, RF, and TabNet.

Preprocessing included SMOTE for class imbalance and *StandardScaler* for normalization. The primary evaluation metric was the weighted F1-score, chosen to balance sensitivity and precision in skewed class distributions. Each model was tuned using a structured parameter grid based on established guidelines. For LR, tuning emphasized L2 regularization with the *saga* solver. RF optimization focused on depth, number of estimators, and feature selection strategies. XGBoost tuning targeted tree depth, learning rate, and subsampling, while TabNet’s search space encompassed attention dimensions, sparsity coefficients, and decision steps. LTCN tuning involved reasoning steps, decay factors, and regularization terms.

Hyperparameter searches were conducted independently for each model using the same cross-validation folds and preprocessing to ensure comparability. The models achieving the highest average weighted

F1-score across folds were selected for final interpretability analysis.³ Table 6 summarizes the key hyperparameters explored for each model. Full tuning grids with tested and selected values are available in Appendix 15.2.

6.1 Explainability Techniques and Attribution Strategies

Intrinsic attributions are obtained from each model’s internal mechanisms, such as coefficient values in LR, learned connection weights in LTCNs, and attention-based feature importances in TabNet. We also extract feature importance scores in RF and XGBoost, applying model-specific SHAP explanations for interpretation. To assess feature importance comprehensively, we use model-agnostic methods—specifically PFI and PMC—for alignment with model-specific methods. PMCs also evaluate the validity of attribution methods. SOFI is exclusively employed in this experiment, compared against SHAP for black-box models, native importances, and PFI. Instead of PMC, we use SOFI, which incorporates a global optimization strategy for more stable and aligned rankings.

6.2 Marginalization Curves and SOFI

Interpretability is a critical requirement in ML, especially in clinical contexts. While many post hoc explanation methods exist, a gap remains in their rigorous evaluation. Most methods offer qualitative insights or feature rankings, but few provide quantitative measures of explanation faithfulness or sparsity in relation to model behavior. To address this, we adopt PMCs as a consistent evaluation framework (Meng et al., 2022). These curves measure how model performance declines as features are sequentially marginalized based on attributed importance; a sharper, more monotonic drop indicates a more faithful explanation. We also evaluate SOFI (Grau & Nápoles, 2024), a method that optimizes for low area under the PMCs while penalizing non-monotonicity. By incorporating this evaluation metric into its objective, SOFI produces sparse and faithful feature rankings. This unifies explanation generation with fidelity assessment, addressing key limitations of prior post hoc methods.

7 RESULTS AND COMPARATIVE EVALUATION

This section evaluates the model’s performance on SMOTE-augmented data. Beyond standard accuracy metrics, we assess generalization, prediction reliability, and class-specific behavior which are important factors in

³ All models used `scikit-learn`, `PyTorch`, `TabNet`, and `XGBoost` libraries.

medical contexts. Performance is evaluated across training, validation, and test sets using Weighted F1 and Cohen’s Kappa, which address class imbalance and measure agreement beyond chance. This analysis highlights the model’s strengths and limitations in supporting reliable and meaningful ASD screening.

7.1 *Model Generalization, Robustness, and Comparative Insights*

Table 1 and Table 2 summarize the models’ performance. RF and XGBoost emerged as the top performers, each achieving test F1-scores exceeding 0.89 and AUC values of 0.93. LR and LTCN showed solid consistency between training and testing, reflecting good generalization. In contrast, TabNet displayed underperformance, particularly on ASD-positive cases.

The training and validation F1 scores, along with their standard deviations, illustrate each model’s generalization ability. As shown in Table 1, RF and XGBoost exhibited minimal variation between training and validation scores (F1 Std: 0.00/0.02 and 0.01/0.02), demonstrating robust performance and a low risk of overfitting. LR and LTCNs also displayed consistent performance (0.01/0.01) indicating stability. Conversely, TabNet showed higher variability (0.01/0.02), correlating with its weaker test performance under SMOTE.

XGBoost achieved the best overall results (F1 = 0.91, AUC = 0.93), featuring the lowest false negative rate and identifying 31 ASD cases effectively. The alignment between validation and test scores confirms its strong generalization ability. RF closely followed with an F1 score of 0.90 and a Kappa of 0.71, showcasing high precision and discriminative power (AUC = 0.93). However, the slight decline from training to test (F1 = 0.94 to 0.90) indicates mild overfitting, possibly affecting its reliability on diverse datasets.

LR performed competitively, with an F1 score of 0.85 and Kappa of 0.62. Although it exhibited elevated false positives, it maintained a strong AUC of 0.93 and stable validation (F1 = 0.84 ± 0.06), making it suitable where transparency is necessary. LTCNs demonstrated solid generalization (F1 = 0.88/0.86, Kappa = 0.63), but its lower AUC (0.84) suggests limited class separability. Removing alpha regularization led to overfitting (Train F1 = 0.93, Test F1 = 0.82). TabNet performed the weakest (F1 = 0.70, AUC = 0.57), misclassifying 29 ASD cases, limiting its clinical applicability despite theoretical potential.

Table 1: Model Performance Summary

Model	Train F1	Validation F1	Test F1	F1 Std (Train/Val)
Logistic Regression	0.86	0.85	0.85	0.01 / 0.01
Random Forest	0.94	0.87	0.90	0.00 / 0.02
TabNet	0.64	0.64	0.70	0.01 / 0.02
XGBOOST	0.94	0.86	0.91	0.01 / 0.02
LTCN	0.90	0.84	0.86	0.01 / 0.01

Table 2: Performance Evaluation Using Kappa Score

Model	Train Kappa	Test Kappa
LR	0.62	0.62
RF	0.83	0.71
TabNet	-0.07	0.12
XGBoost	0.82	0.74
LTCN	0.68	0.63

7.2 Gender Evaluation

In addition to overall metrics, subgroup-level performance was analyzed to assess fairness. As shown in Appendix 15.3, models displayed significant gender disparity. Positive Prediction Rates (PPR) for males were consistently higher, with RF and XGBoost showing a 19.6% gap. Gender-specific F1-scores revealed further imbalances: XGBoost had the most consistent performance (F1: 0.82 for males and 0.76 for females), while TabNet showed the largest discrepancy (F1: 0.31 vs. 0.14). These findings emphasize the need for subgroup-sensitive evaluation in clinical ML applications.

Additional visualizations—including confusion matrices, Precision–Recall (PR) curves, and gender distribution plots—are provided in Appendix 15.3. These offer insights into model-specific classification behavior, particularly regarding sensitivity, class trade-offs, and fairness. A summary of the best-performing hyperparameters for each model is also included to support reproducibility and transparency.

Furthermore, an analysis using Gaussian noise injection was performed to assess model robustness under data perturbation. Due to word count constraints, detailed results and discussions are available in Appendix 16.5.

8 FEATURE IMPORTANCE ANALYSIS (WITH SMOTE)

8.1 *Feature Attribution Analysis*

Beyond performance metrics and gender-based analysis, we assess multiple attribution methods to compare importance scores across models and examine the consistency between model-specific and model-agnostic explanations. This includes PFI, PMC, SHAP, and native attributions. Comparative visualizations are provided for all techniques; when results are unclear or inconsistent, additional plots aid interpretation.

Native importance derives from each model’s internal structure: RF and XGBoost expose built-in importance scores, LR uses absolute coefficients, TabNet aggregates attention masks, and LTCN estimates importance via internal dynamics.

PFI measures impact by assessing performance drops after permuting feature values but is sensitive to feature correlations and noise.

PMC replaces features with their marginal mean and observes changes in F1 score, avoiding unrealistic inputs but assuming feature independence.

SHAP applies a game-theoretic approach to allocate prediction contributions. TreeExplainer is used for compatible models like RF and XGBoost, enabling both local and global interpretability.

To ensure comparability, we normalize all scores and visualize the top 10 features ranked by native importance, highlighting agreement and divergence between methods, and offering deeper insight into model behavior and feature relevance.

8.2 *Model-Specific Observations*

Figures 7 and 8 show feature attributions for LR, separated to reflect differences between native importance and post-hoc methods accordingly.

Notably, **A4_Score** and **result** exhibit high importance according to the model’s native attributions, yet appear neutral when assessed by external methods, suggesting a discrepancy in their perceived predictive value. Similarly, while the feature *austim* receives a positive coefficient from the native model, it is consistently evaluated as negatively important by both PFI and PMC. Moreover, external interpretability methods tend to attribute importance across a broader set of features, in contrast to the native coefficients, which focus more narrowly on behavioral indicators. These divergences underscore the fundamental differences in how internal model attributions and model-agnostic approaches define and compute feature importance, emphasizing the need for caution when interpreting model behavior.

Figure 7: These values reflect the internal model coefficients and represent how strongly each feature contributes to the decision boundary during training such as result.

Figure 8: Feature importance derived from PMC and PFI for LR reveals agreement on key features such as *age*, while both methods assign a negative influence to *gender* and *austim*. However, they diverge in their interpretation of *relation*, where opposite patterns of influence are observed because of methodological differences.

LTCNs (Fig. 9) assigns maximum normalized importance to all top-ranked features via native attribution, likely due to uniform contributions from SVD-based initialization. However, external methods differentiate feature impacts more distinctly. Notably, demographic variables such as

Age and **gender** are prioritized by both PFI and PMC methods, with only marginal distinctions observed between their respective importances. For a detailed explanation of how SVD initialization leads to uniform importance attribution, see Appendix 16.6.

Figure 9: Native scores are uniformly high, while external methods reveal more variation, especially for demographic features. A6_score, age, gender and A8_score was the features leveraged by all three methods.

Figures 10 and 11 illustrate a strong alignment across methods in the prioritization of key features, notably **result**, **A6_Score**, and **A9_Score**, for RF model. However, the PMC method introduces notable reordering, placing increased emphasis on **A5_Score**, **A6_Score**, and **ethnicity**. While these features are also recognized by other attribution techniques, PMC's relatively higher importance values suggest its sensitivity to subtler feature contributions.

In contrast, Figure 12 presents results from the XGBoost model, where the native feature attributions display a more distributed emphasis, particularly highlighting **A9_Score**. Both PMC and PFI methods similarly assign importance to a broad range of behavioral indicators. Interestingly, while PFI continues to emphasize **result**, PMC appears to downplay its role in the XGBoost context. SHAP, on the other hand, consistently identifies the most influential features across both models, with a pronounced focus on items related to **A10 scores**, aligning closely with other interpretability approaches.

Figure 10: Native and PFI are consistent for most features, while PMC highlights others not dominant, such as ethnicity, A6_score and A5_score.

Figure 11: SHAP prioritizes features such as $A3_Score$, $A4_Score$, and $A9_Score$, closely aligning with the native feature importances. This agreement is expected given SHAP’s model-specific nature. In contrast, PMC continues to diverge by assigning greater importance to alternative features, a pattern not observed with PFI, which remains consistent with the native analysis.

Figure 12: A strong agreement between model-agnostic and native importance is observed, particularly for behavioral indicators which capture robust influence on performance.

Figure 13: The features *A9_Score*, *A4_Score*, and *A3_Score* exhibit the strongest influence on the model’s output, with *A9_Score* being particularly dominant. This aligns well with the importance rankings derived from external methods (see Figure 12). Interestingly, features such as *result* also show notable impact in the SHAP analysis, despite receiving little emphasis from the native model and being largely overlooked by PMC.

The TabNet model (Figure 14) exhibits significant divergence across attribution methods. Its native importance highlights scoring-related features like *A6_Score* and *A4_Score*, while also assigning moderate weight to less commonly emphasized variables such as *used_app_before*, *A7_Score*, *jaundice*, and *gender*. In contrast, both PMC and PFI concentrate more on behavioral indicators. The native attributions in TabNet are unevenly distributed, resulting in lower average importance per feature.

While black-box models typically show stronger alignment between model-agnostic and native methods, TabNet and LTCNs stand out by leveraging broader feature sets, capturing more complex patterns. Model-agnostic approaches, however, often emphasize a narrower subset of inputs, as seen in TabNet’s focus on specific behavioral features through PMC

and PFI. Notably, LR is unique in producing negative feature attributions, providing a different perspective on interpretability. These variations highlight how each model architecture uniquely encodes and prioritizes features in the context of explainability.

Figure 14: TabNet feature importance comparison. Native attribution distributes importance across multiple features, while post-hoc methods focus primarily on behavioral indicators.

9 PERFORMANCE MARGINALIZATION CURVES WITH SMOTE

To assess the effectiveness of feature attribution methods, we use PMCs. These curves simulate feature removal by progressively neutralizing inputs based on each method’s importance ranking. After each step, model performance is re-evaluated using the weighted F1 score, producing a degradation curve for every model-method pair. To quantify informativeness, we compute the AUC of our PMCs. A lower AUC indicates a sharper performance drop, suggesting the method accurately ranked influential features. Conversely, a higher AUC implies minimal performance impact, signaling weaker alignment with the model’s true feature sensitivity. In this analysis, we compare four attribution methods, PFI, native importance, SHAP (for black-box models), and SOFI, based on their corresponding AUC values.

Table 3: AUC Scores of Feature Marginalization Curves

Model	Native	SOFI	PFI	SHAP
LR	13.34	11.18	14.54	–
RF	6.49	5.57	6.27	6.91
XGBoost	5.93	4.66	5.32	5.52
LTCN	9.17	7.92	11.40	–
TabNet	9.77	6.70	7.67	–

The results in Table 3 reveal consistent trends across architectures. In **RF** and **XGBoost**, SOFI achieves the lowest AUCs of 5.57 and 4.66 respectively, which indicates that its ranked features align most closely with the model’s actual decision boundaries. PFI and Native perform moderately well, while SHAP, despite its theoretical grounding in tree-based models, shows slightly flatter curves and hence higher AUCs.

For **TabNet** and **LTCNs**, the advantage of SOFI is even more pronounced. Its AUC scores (6.70 in TabNet and 7.92 in LTCN) are significantly lower than those of PFI and Native, illustrating SOFI’s ability to navigate more abstract feature spaces where traditional importance measures may struggle. In **LR**, the AUCs are generally higher, reflecting flatter flip curves. This is expected due to the model’s linear nature and inherent transparency. Nevertheless, SOFI still outperforms both Native and PFI, suggesting that it maintains value even in simpler models—that model-agnostic methods can still provide added insight where native coefficients might not fully capture practical feature influence. For detailed marginalization curves corresponding to these results, see Appendix 16.1.

10 EVALUATION WITHOUT SMOTE OVERSAMPLING

This section presents a detailed evaluation of all models trained **without the use of SMOTE** oversampling. The goal is to assess model performance using the same metrics as before in order to provide a fair comparison with SMOTE-based results and to better understand each model’s capabilities when learning from the original imbalanced dataset.

10.1 Performance Comparison

Table 4 summarizes model performance without **SMOTE**, while Table 11 lists the best hyperparameters selected through grid search in Appendix 15.4. Among all models, **XGBoost** achieved the highest test F1 score (0.87) and a

strong Kappa (0.63), indicating a well-balanced trade-off between precision and recall. **RF** and **LTCN** followed closely (F1: 0.86, Kappa: 0.60), demonstrating comparable robustness. **LR** also performed competitively (F1: 0.86) and showed the lowest validation F1 standard deviation, establishing it as a stable and interpretable baseline. In contrast, **TabNet** yielded the weakest performance (F1: 0.70, Kappa: 0.12), suggesting learning instability, further evidenced by its negative training Kappa. The unregularized **LTCNs** model showed signs of overfitting: despite high training scores (F1: 0.94, Kappa: 0.82), test performance declined significantly (F1: 0.82, Kappa: 0.50). These results highlight the advantages of ensemble models and well-regularized architectures such as RF, XGBoost, LR, and LTCNs over deeper models like TabNet, particularly in data-limited settings without resampling.

Additional visual diagnostics, including precision-recall curves, ROC curves, gender distribution analyses, and confusion matrices, align with the non-oversampled setting. Gender-specific evaluation revealed higher recall and PPR for male individuals across models. SMOTE improved female detection in some cases, though disparities persisted. See Appendix 15.4 for full metrics and confusion matrices.

Table 4: Model performance summary without SMOTE

Model	Train F1	Train F1 Std	Vld F1	Vld F1 Std	Test F1	Test Kappa
LR	0.89	0.01	0.86	0.02	0.86	0.59
RF	0.92	0.00	0.86	0.02	0.86	0.60
TabNet	0.64	0.01	0.64	0.02	0.70	0.12
XGBOOST	0.91	0.01	0.86	0.02	0.87	0.63
LTCN	0.90	0.01	0.87	0.03	0.86	0.60

11 FEATURE IMPORTANCE ANALYSIS (WITHOUT SMOTE)

To assess how class imbalance affects interpretability, we re-evaluated feature importance on the original dataset using the same attribution methods. This comparison helps identify stable features and reveals model sensitivity under these conditions. Notably, combining Native, PFI, and PMC attributions into one plot may obscure differences due to varying scales, particularly in LR and LTCNs; thus, separate visualizations are provided.

In LR (Figure 15), key features included **relation**, **ethnicity**, and **A4_score**. The native importance emphasized features like **A4_score** and **A6_score**, reflecting trends observed under SMOTE (Figure 16). Comparing models

trained with and without SMOTE revealed noticeable differences in feature rankings. For instance, **relation** displayed a negative influence in PFI under SMOTE but gained prominence without oversampling. **A4_score** consistently ranked as important, while **A8_score** showed a strong influence in PFI with greater variance, indicating context-dependent importance. The **result** variable, prioritized by the native model and PMC, was downplayed or negatively weighted by PFI, highlighting inconsistencies among interpretive approaches.

Figure 15: Features like *relation*, *ethnicity*, and **A4_score** show strong agreement between methods. In contrast, **result** and *used_app_before* receive negative importance in PFI, but PMC assigns a positive role to **result** and downplays *used_app_before*. This contrast reflects differences between marginalization and permutation-based approaches.

Figure 16: Behavioral screening items such as *A4_Score*, *A6_Score*, and *A3_Score* dominate the ranking, suggesting strong alignment with ASD assessment criteria. Binary features like *austim* and *jaundice* are present but carry less weight in the model’s decision-making.

As shown in Figure 17, the LTCN model’s native importance emphasizes features like autism, gender, ethnicity, and various behavioral indicators. Both PMC and PFI also highlight the *A10* questions. Notably, the *A1* score shows opposite effects—positive in LTCN’s native importance but negative in the model-agnostic methods. With SMOTE, native importance continues to capture a broader feature set, including gender, ethnicity, and *used_app_before*. In contrast, external methods focus more on behavioral indicators and autism, though only **A4_score** overlaps with the native importance, suggesting differing feature priorities across methods.

Figure 17: The model places emphasis not only on behavioral features but also on demographic and categorical variables such as *autism*, *ethnicity*, and *gender*, in contrast to external methods that prioritize behavioral indicators. This suggests that LTCN’s structural weighting may favor broad identity-related features over task-specific signals.

Figure 18: While both methods identify *A4_Score*, *A9_Score*, and *A10_Score* as influential, they differ on others: PMC highlights *autism* and *result*, whereas PFI assigns more weight to *A5_Score* and further emphasizes *A10_Score*. Negative importance values for features like *country_of_res* and *A1_Score* suggest that their perturbation may enhance model performance, indicating potential noise or redundancy.

In Figure 20, the Random Forest (RF) model shows strong alignment across interpretation methods. High-ranking features such as **result**,

A6_Score, and **A3_Score** consistently appear across the Native model, PFI, and PMC. SHAP values, in particular, align closely with the native importance—prioritizing **result**, **A9_Score**, and **A3_Score**, which is expected given SHAP’s model-specific nature. Under SMOTE, these core features remain prominent, highlighting RF’s interpretive stability across sampling strategies

Figure 19: Behavioral features such as *A3_Score*, *A6_Score*, and *A9_Score* dominate, aligning with top-ranked features in Figure 20. However, SHAP assigns less importance to *result*, compare to other methods.

Figure 20: The *result* feature dominates, followed by several screening scores such as *A6_Score*, *A3_Score*, and *A9_Score*. This confirms RF’s strength in modeling interactions among questionnaire-based inputs.

XGBoost exhibits a hybrid pattern, as shown in Figure 22. Core features like *A9_Score*, other behavioral indicators, and *result* consistently rank high across methods. However, beyond these top features, the attribution diverges, with lower-ranked variables differing by method. Compared to the SMOTE-applied version, the key features remain largely the same, although there is a noticeably stronger emphasis on *result* in the absence of SMOTE.

Figure 21: Features such as *A9_Score*, *A4_Score*, and *result* exhibit strong positive contributions to ASD predictions when their values are high, supporting their top rankings in other methods. However, it places greater emphasis on *A3_Score*, whereas other methods prioritize *result*

Figure 22: XGBoost shows strong agreement across methods for top features, with greater divergence in mid-ranked ones, and consistent alignment in the least important features.

TabNet focuses on similar features regardless of SMOTE usage. This suggests that SMOTE does not significantly alter which features are emphasized, but rather affects the relative importance attributed to each one. As before, all methods focus on behavioral indicators, while the native importance captures a broader feature set.

Figure 23: TabNet native attribution highlights both behavioral and auxiliary features, while post-hoc methods focus primarily on specific behavioral indicators.

Across models and attribution methods, key behavioral features—such as `A3_Score`, `A4_Score`, `A6_Score`, `A9_Score`, and `result`—consistently emerge as primary drivers of ASD prediction. While demographic variables like `autism`, `gender`, and `ethnicity` are notable in native importances, post-hoc methods often focus more on task-specific behavioral indicators. SHAP aligns closely with native importances in tree-based models, reflecting its model-aware approach. Notably, RF and XGBoost demonstrate higher interpretive stability, maintaining consistent feature rankings with and without SMOTE. This indicates that these models are more resilient to class imbalance in both prediction and interpretation.

12 PERFORMANCE MARGINALIZATION CURVES WITHOUT SMOTE

To assess attribution method performance under real-world class imbalance, we compute the AUC of PMCs. The experiment uses the same attribution methods as in the usage of oversampling.

SOFI outperforms all other methods across all models, achieving the lowest AUC scores and effectively prioritizing the most influential features. Generally, we observe higher AUC values for most interpretability methods compared to their counterparts with oversampling, suggesting that the use of SMOTE may enhance feature attribution by revealing more meaningful patterns. In simpler models such as LR, SOFI shows a smaller AUC (9.84) across all methods. Notably, it is the only model where the AUC is lower without SMOTE, implying that oversampling may not aid feature attribution in this specific case.

For ensemble models, SOFI continues to dominate, achieving the lowest AUC values (8.86 and 8.73), closely followed by SHAP. However, in the presence of SMOTE, the gap in AUC between SOFI and other methods tends to increase, indicating greater variability. TabNet again appears unaffected by SMOTE, consistent with prior observations on its feature attributions. In contrast, LTCN generally exhibits higher AUC values without SMOTE, though SOFI still prevails, suggesting its optimization mechanism remains effective in validating feature importance, even under different data conditions. Across all settings, the marginalization curves for each method eventually stabilize, indicating that once top-ranked features are removed, the remaining features contribute minimally to model performance. For detailed marginalization curves generated without SMOTE, see Appendix 16.2.

Table 5: AUC Scores of Feature Marginalization Curves

Model	Native	SOFI	PFI	SHAP
LR	10.68	9.84	11.93	–
RF	9.74	8.86	9.06	8.95
XGBoost	9.49	8.73	8.79	8.84
LTCN	10.16	9.39	9.73	–
TabNet	9.77	6.70	7.67	–

13 DISCUSSION

This section provides a critical interpretation of the results presented in Section 7, with direct reference to the research objectives formulated in Section 3. Beyond evaluating model performance and interpretability alignment, this discussion aims to contextualize the findings within the existing body of literature, reflect on the broader scientific and societal contributions, and outline key limitations. The section concludes with targeted recommendations for future research in interpretable ML for ASD diagnosis and similar clinical applications.

13.1 Answers to Research Questions

RQ1: *How do ML models perform in the classification of Autism Spectrum Disorder?*

This question addressed through the evaluation of three sub-questions that examine model accuracy, attribution alignment, and interpretability fidelity. Each sub-question targets a distinct dimension of model performance which enables a more comprehensive and structured assessment.

SQ1: *How do different ML models for ASD classification perform in terms of predictive accuracy, as measured by F1-score, AUC, and Cohen’s Kappa?*

The ML models evaluated in this study exhibited limited variation in predictive performance across different levels of complexity and class rebalancing strategies. Ensemble methods, particularly RF and XGBoost, delivered the most consistent results, with XGBoost slightly outperforming RF, especially under imbalanced conditions. Prior studies have also identified XGBoost’s strength in similar contexts. For example, Imani et al. (2025) reported that XGBoost combined with SMOTE achieved the highest

F1 and MCC scores at imbalance levels between 15% and 1%, significantly outperforming RF. Similarly, Mittal et al. (2024) demonstrated XGBoost’s ability to detect subtle behavioral and demographic indicators of ASD risk. While our results align with these findings in terms of predictive accuracy, we extend this line of work by evaluating attribution fidelity — a dimension largely absent in earlier ASD classification studies.

Additionally, Kanchana and Khilar (2022) found RF to be the top-performing model in a dataset of 704 ASD cases, outperforming logistic regression (LR), decision trees, and Naïve Bayes. Our results support RF’s robustness but show that explanation quality, especially with SOFI, can vary even in accurate models. This emphasizes the need to evaluate both accuracy and interpretability in clinical applications. XGBoost and RF performed well on structured, imbalanced data. LR, known for transparency, also performed well with SMOTE, producing low false negative rates important for ASD screening (Okoye et al., 2023), consistent with (Jayaprakash & Kanimozhiselvi, 2024). However, LR struggles with non-linear patterns (Labhade-Kumar, 2024).

TabNet performed poorly, likely due to unstable attention-based feature selection in small or synthetic datasets, unlike in (Kanász et al., 2024), where richer data improved performance. LTCNs, though interpretable, showed class bias and near-linear AUCs. Their strengths in other studies (Nápoles et al., 2021) were reduced under noisy feature interactions and class overlap.

SQ2: *To what extent do model-specific and model-agnostic feature importance methods agree across interpretable, quasi-interpretable, and black-box models, in terms of feature prioritization?*

The alignment between native and model-agnostic feature importance varied significantly across models. Notably, ensemble methods like RF and XGBoost, typically seen as black box models, showed strong consistency with post-hoc attribution methods. This suggests that convergence among different explanation approaches may indicate underlying model stability. These findings align with research by (Yasodhara et al., 2021), indicating that global feature importance can become unstable in weaker models. Thus, agreement among attribution techniques could serve as an indicator of model robustness and trustworthiness.

Conversely, interpretable models like LTCNs and LR (our baseline model) exhibited weaker alignment between native and model-agnostic explanations. For example, LR’s native coefficients highlighted behavioral features, while post-hoc methods emphasized variables such as *gender*, *contry_of_res*, and *relation*-factors overlooked by other models. This raises fairness concerns, particularly since *gender* is a known bias factor in ASD

diagnosis (Supekar et al., 2022). Using model-agnostic explanations for transparent models like LR may produce misleading interpretations (Mittal et al., 2024). Furthermore, $A4_score$ ranked highly in native outputs but was minimized by agnostic tools, illustrating LR’s limited capacity to capture feature interactions (Lipton, 2016).

LTCNs showed similar mismatches, with native importance scores focusing on broader structural features and post-hoc tools highlighting behavioral indicators. After employing SMOTE, demographic features partially converged, though $A1$ remained misaligned. This suggests that native methods may identify underlying structural patterns that model-agnostic tools miss, a challenge also noted in hybrid models (Hooshyar & Yang, 2024). Post-hoc methods are sensitive to noise and model instability (Molnar et al., 2021). In TabNet, native attributions were evenly distributed, while SHAP and PFI focused heavily on $A10$ questions, illustrating PFI’s sensitivity to feature correlations (Molnar, 2022). This emphasizes the need for validating explanations with model logic and domain knowledge, especially in clinical contexts (Turbé et al., 2023).

SQ3: *Which feature importance method reports the most accurate explanations, as measured by the performance-marginalization curve?*

SOFI consistently demonstrated the most faithful attributions across various models, evidenced by the AUC of PMCs. In ensemble models like XGBoost and RF, SOFI achieved AUCs of 4.66 and 5.57, respectively, indicating a strong alignment between feature rankings and model logic. The notable performance drop when top features were marginalized underscores SOFI’s capacity to identify high-impact inputs, consistent with its design for sparse and faithful explanations (Grau & Nápoles, 2024).

In comparison, PFI and SHAP performed reasonably well in ensemble settings but exhibited flatter degradation curves. In RF, PFI and native importance had similar AUCs of 6.27 and 6.49, while SHAP’s AUC was 6.91. For LR, overall attribution quality was lower, reflected in flatter curves and higher AUCs. SOFI outperformed LR’s coefficients (11.18 vs. 13.34), suggesting coefficient magnitude may not reliably indicate functional importance, especially in the context of multicollinearity (Senaviratna & Cooray, 2019).

In grey-box models, LTCNs and TabNet showed intermediate fidelity, with SOFI leading at 7.92 for LTCNs and 6.70 for TabNet, where TabNet’s PFI also performed well. LTCNs’ native attributions were more informative than LR’s but less effective than post-hoc methods, indicating that architectural features aid partial transparency (Balci et al., 2023). Without SMOTE, AUC scores improved across models, revealing that data bal-

ance enhances attribution stability; yet, SOFI consistently outperformed alternative methods (Dervovic et al., 2024; Madsen et al., 2024).

13.2 *Emphasizing Societal and Scientific Impact*

In this study, we addressed the need for interpretability in ML (Blackman & Veerapen, 2025), especially in high-stakes domains like ASD diagnosis. As ML becomes more common in healthcare, accuracy alone is insufficient—models must also be transparent, fair, and trustworthy (Vimbi et al., 2025). Our goal was to evaluate how well model-agnostic methods align with model-specific ones, using a validation framework based on PMCs. This allowed us to compare interpretability tools and assess whether their outputs reflect actual model sensitivities. Our findings align with prior work showing ensemble models perform well on tabular healthcare data (Gill et al., 2022), particularly under class imbalance and noise. While earlier studies focus on accuracy, few rigorously assess interpretability methods (Doshi-Velez & Kim, 2017). By applying PMC-based validation, we contribute a reproducible framework for measuring explanation fidelity, improving on subjective comparisons by using AUC. The societal relevance is clear: early ASD detection is crucial (Elder et al., 2017), yet often biased against females (Leedham et al., 2020). Our fairness analysis revealed consistent gender disparities, with females under-identified across all models. SMOTE improved recall for females but increased false positives, underscoring the fairness–performance trade-off. These results highlight the need for explainable, accountable AI in clinical settings, where diagnostic errors carry serious consequences. These findings highlight the need for explainable AI in clinical settings, where diagnostic errors have serious consequences.

13.3 *Limitations*

While this study provides a structured evaluation of model performance and interpretability in ASD classification, several limitations must be acknowledged. The use of synthetic data, while practical for prototyping, limits ecological validity. It lacks the variability, noise, and complexity of real clinical datasets, potentially inflating both performance and interpretability. The relatively small sample size (N=800) also increases the risk of overfitting, especially in complex models, potentially reducing feature attribution stability. Lack of external validation also limits generalizability.

While the binary classification framework may appear simpler, it fails to capture the inherent complexity and spectrum-based nature of ASD. This limitation is also reflected in the suboptimal performance observed across

models, suggesting that future work should explore multi-class approaches that better align with the dimensional characteristics of ASD. While SMOTE improved recall for underrepresented subgroups such as females, it may have introduced synthetic patterns that distort feature attribution, particularly for post-hoc methods like SHAP and PFI. These techniques, though common, can give a misleading impression of model transparency when applied to noisy or unstable inputs. Although ensemble models like XGBoost performed well, their opacity challenges interpretability in clinical use. In addition, computational constraints limited hyperparameter tuning to fixed search spaces, which may have impacted both model performance and explanation consistency. Persistent gender disparities highlight the need for fairness-aware modeling and real-world validation in future research.

13.4 *Future Work*

This thesis advances research on interpretable machine learning for ASD screening, though several important directions remain open. A primary limitation is the use of synthetic data. While this supports controlled experimentation and protects privacy, synthetic datasets cannot fully capture the complexity of clinical data. Future work should validate both model performance and interpretability—particularly SOFI—on real-world datasets to assess robustness and clinical utility.

Given ASD's developmental nature, future models should explore longitudinal data to reflect evolving traits across life stages. Temporal architectures, such as recurrent or attention-based networks, may enhance early detection and monitoring. Integrating multimodal data—such as speech, facial expressions, or movement—also offers promise. These behavioral signals, often absent in structured questionnaires, could improve diagnostic accuracy and explanation fidelity. Gender disparities in recall highlight persistent fairness concerns. The models consistently underperformed for female individuals, emphasizing the need for fairness-aware training and evaluation. Techniques such as subgroup reweighting or adversarial debiasing should be considered to reduce predictive gaps across gender, age, and ethnicity, promoting equitable deployment.

Finally, interpretability research must include insights from clinicians, caregivers, and individuals with ASD. Human-centered evaluations are essential to ensure that model explanations are not only technically valid but also comprehensible and aligned with real-world diagnostic needs.

14 CONCLUSION

As ML enters clinical practice, the demand for models that are accurate, interpretable, and fair increases. This thesis introduced a framework using PMCs to assess explanation quality in ASD diagnosis. Ensemble models—especially XGBoost with SOFI—offered strong predictive performance and consistent interpretability. Signs of overfitting in RF highlight the need for robust validation. By linking model behavior to explanation fidelity, this work supports trustworthy clinical AI. Future research should test these findings on real data and pursue deployment in transparent, equitable tools.

REFERENCES

- Alqaysi, M. E., Albahri, A. S., & Hamid, R. A. (2024). Evaluation and benchmarking of hybrid machine learning models for autism spectrum disorder diagnosis using a 2-tuple linguistic neutrosophic fuzzy sets-based decision-making model. *Neural Computing and Applications*, 36, 18161–18200. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00521-024-09905-6>
- Alves, C. L., Toutain, T. G. L. d. O., Aguiar, P. d. C., Pineda, A. M., Roster, K., Thielemann, C., Porto, J. A. M., & Rodrigues, F. A. (2023). Diagnosis of autism spectrum disorder based on functional brain networks and machine learning. *Scientific Reports*, 13(1), 8072. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-34650-6>
- Arik, S. O., & Pfister, T. (2021). Tabnet: Attentive interpretable tabular learning. *Proceedings of the AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence*, 35(8), 6679–6687.
- Babalola, T., Sanguedolce, G., Dipper, L., & Botting, N. (2024). Barriers and facilitators of healthcare access for autistic children in the uk: A systematic review [Published: 05 January 2024]. *Review Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40489-023-00420-3>
- Balcan, M.-F., & Sharma, D. (2025). Learning accurate and interpretable tree-based models. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2405.15911>
- Balçı, A. T., Ebeid, M. M., Benos, P. V., Kostka, D., & Chikina, M. (2023). An intrinsically interpretable neural network architecture for sequence-to-function learning. *Bioinformatics*, 39(Suppl_1), i413–i422. <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btad271>
- Bell, A., Solano-Kamaiko, I. R., Nov, O., & Stoyanovich, J. (2022). It's just not that simple: An empirical study of the accuracy-explainability trade-off in machine learning for public policy. *Proceedings of the*

- 2022 ACM Conference on Fairness, Accountability, and Transparency (FAccT '22), 1221–1233. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3531146.3533090>
- Blackman, J., & Veerapen, R. (2025). On the practical, ethical, and legal necessity of clinical artificial intelligence explainability: An examination of key arguments. *BMC Medical Informatics and Decision Making*, 25, 111. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12911-025-02345-6>
- Bokka, Y., Mohan, R. N. V. J., & Naik, M. C. (2024). SHAP-Driven Interpretability of Autism Risk in Pregnancy Using Explainable AI. *2024 International Conference on Integrated Intelligence and Communication Systems (ICIICS)*. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICIICS63763.2024.10859415>
- Chen, T., & Guestrin, C. (2016). Xgboost: A scalable tree boosting system. *Proceedings of the 22nd ACM SIGKDD International Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining*, 785–794. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2939672.2939785>
- Cheong, Y. J., Bae, J., Lee, S., Hyeong, R. J., Kosaka, H., & Lyu, I. (2024). Prediction of autism spectrum disorder using epigenetic, brain, and sensory behavioral factors. *Proceedings of the 2024 12th International Winter Conference on Brain-Computer Interface (BCI)*. <https://doi.org/10.1109/BCI60775.2024.10480486>
- Cortese, S., Bellato, A., Gabellone, A., Marzulli, L., Matera, E., Parlatini, V., Petruzzelli, M. G., Persico, A. M., Delorme, R., Fusar-Poli, P., Gosling, C. J., Solmi, M., & Margari, L. (2025). Latest clinical frontiers related to autism diagnostic strategies. *Cell Reports Medicine*, 6(2), 101916. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.xcrm.2024.101916>
- den Broeck, G. V., Lykov, A., Schleich, M., & Suci, D. (2021). On the tractability of shap explanations. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2009.08634>
- Dervovic, D., Lécué, F., Marchesotti, N., & Magazzeni, D. (2024). Are logistic models really interpretable? <https://arxiv.org/abs/2406.13427>
- Doshi-Velez, F., & Kim, B. (2017). Towards a rigorous science of interpretable machine learning. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1702.08608*. <https://arxiv.org/abs/1702.08608>
- Duda, M., Ma, R., Haber, N., & Wall, D. P. (2016). Use of machine learning for behavioral distinction of autism and adhd. *Translational Psychiatry*, 6(2), e732. <https://doi.org/10.1038/tp.2015.221>
- Elder, J. H., Kreider, C. M., Brasher, S. N., & Ansell, M. (2017). Clinical impact of early diagnosis of autism on the prognosis and parent–child relationships. *Psychology Research and Behavior Management*, 10, 283–292. <https://doi.org/10.2147/PRBM.S117499>
- Geb, D. (2022). Autism spectrum disorder prediction. <https://www.kaggle.com/code/desalegngeb/autism-spectrum-disorder-prediction>

- Gill, M., Anderson, R., Hu, H., Bennamoun, M., Petereit, J., Valliyodan, B., Nguyen, H. T., Batley, J., Bayer, P. E., & Edwards, D. (2022). Machine learning models outperform deep learning models, provide interpretation and facilitate feature selection for soybean trait prediction. *GigaScience*, *11*, giaco20. <https://doi.org/10.1093/gigascience/giaco20>
- Grau, I., & Nápoles, G. (2024). Sparseness-optimized feature importance. *Proceedings of the xAI Conference 2024*.
- Halabaku, E., & Bytyçi, E. (2024). Overfitting in machine learning: A comparative analysis of decision trees and random forests [Published Online: 23 December 2024]. *Intelligent Automation & Soft Computing*, *38*(3), TBD. <https://doi.org/10.32604/iasc.2024.059429>
- Heinsfeld, A. S., Franco, A. R., Craddock, R. C., Buchweitz, A., & Meneguzzi, F. (2017). Identification of autism spectrum disorder using deep learning and the abide dataset. *NeuroImage: Clinical*, *17*, 16–23. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nicl.2017.08.017>
- Holzinger, A., Langs, G., Denk, H., Zatloukal, K., & Müller, H. (2019). Causability and explainability of artificial intelligence in medicine. *Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Data Mining and Knowledge Discovery*, *9*(4), e1312. <https://doi.org/10.1002/widm.1312>
- Hooshyar, D., & Yang, Y. (2024). Problems with shap and lime in interpretable ai for education: A comparative study of post-hoc explanations and neural-symbolic rule extraction. *IEEE Access*, *12*, 137472–137490. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2024.3463948>
- Huang, C.-Y., Chen, K.-S., Lee, K.-Y., Lin, C.-H., & Chen, K.-L. (2023). Different autism measures targeting different severity levels in children with autism spectrum disorder. *European Archives of Psychiatry and Clinical Neuroscience*, *274*(1), 27–33. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00406-023-01673-z>
- Hung, X., & Marques-Silva, J. (2024). On the failings of shapley values for explainability. *International Journal of Approximate Reasoning*, *171*, 109112. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijar.2023.109112>
- Imani, M., Beikmohammadi, A., & Arabnia, H. R. (2025). Comprehensive analysis of random forest and xgboost performance with smote, adasyn, and gnus under varying imbalance levels. *Technologies*, *13*(3), 88. <https://doi.org/10.3390/technologies13030088>
- Javed, H., El-Sappagh, S., & Abuhmed, T. (2025). Robustness in deep learning models for medical diagnostics: Security and adversarial challenges towards robust ai applications [Accepted: 12 October 2024. Published online: 8 November 2024.]. *Artificial Intelligence Review*, *58*(1), 12. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10462-024-11005-9>

- Jayaprakash, D., & Kanimozhiselvi, C. (2024). Multinomial logistic regression method for early detection of autism spectrum disorders [Open access, under CC license]. *Measurement: Sensors*, 33, 101125. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.measen.2024.101125>
- Kanász, R., Drotár, P., Gnip, P., & Zoričák, M. (2024). Clash of titans on imbalanced data: Tabnet vs xgboost. *Proceedings of the 2024 IEEE Conference on Artificial Intelligence (CAI)*, 320–325. <https://doi.org/10.1109/CAI59869.2024.00068>
- Kanchana, A., & Khilar, R. (2022). Prediction of autism spectrum disorder using random forest classifier in adults, 242–249. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICCCMLA56841.2022.9989304>
- Labhade-Kumar, N. (2024). Study of supervised logistic regression algorithm. 13, 227–230.
- Leedham, A., Thompson, A. R., Smith, R., & Freeth, M. (2020). “i was exhausted trying to figure it out”: The experiences of females receiving an autism diagnosis in middle to late adulthood. *Autism*, 24(1), 135–146. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1362361319853442>
- Lipton, Z. C. (2016). The mythos of model interpretability. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1606.03490*. <https://arxiv.org/abs/1606.03490>
- Liu, Y., Zhao, Q., Zhao, L., Liu, Y., & Li, X. (2025). Modeling temporal dependencies in brain functional connectivity to identify autism spectrum disorders based on heterogeneous rs-fmri data. *Experimental Neurobiology*, 34(2), 77–86. <https://doi.org/10.5607/en24028>
- Lord, C., Elsabbagh, M., Baird, G., & Veenstra-Vanderweele, J. (2018). Autism spectrum disorder. *The Lancet*, 392(10146), 508–520. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(18\)31129-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(18)31129-2)
- Lundberg, S. M., & Lee, S.-I. (2017). A unified approach to interpreting model predictions. In I. Guyon, U. V. Luxburg, S. Bengio, H. Wallach, R. Fergus, S. Vishwanathan, & R. Garnett (Eds.), *Advances in neural information processing systems* (Vol. 30). Curran Associates, Inc. https://proceedings.neurips.cc/paper_files/paper/2017/file/8a20a8621978632d76c43dfd28b67767-Paper.pdf
- Madsen, A., Lakkaraju, H., Reddy, S., & Chandar, S. (2024). Interpretability needs a new paradigm [Version 2, last revised 13 Nov 2024]. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2405.05386*. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2405.05386>
- Mainas, F., Golosio, B., Retico, A., & Oliva, P. (2024). Exploring autism spectrum disorder: A comparative study of traditional classifiers and deep learning classifiers to analyze functional connectivity measures from a multicenter dataset. *Applied Sciences*, 14(17), 7632. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app14177632>

- Meng, C., Trinh, L., Xu, N., Enouen, J., & Liu, Y. (2022). Interpretability and fairness evaluation of deep learning models on MIMIC-IV dataset. *Scientific Reports*, *12*(1), 7166. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-022-11012-2>
- Mittal, K., Gill, K. S., Rajput, K., & Singh, V. (2024). Utilizing machine learning and employing the xgboost classification technique for evaluating the likelihood of autism spectrum disorder (asd). *2024 5th International Conference for Emerging Technology (INCET)*, 1–5. <https://doi.org/10.1109/INCET61516.2024.10593455>
- Molnar, C. (2022). *Interpretable machine learning*. Leanpub. <https://christophm.github.io/interpretable-ml-book/>
- Molnar, C., König, G., Herbringer, J., Freiesleben, T., Dandl, S., Scholbeck, C. A., Casalicchio, G., Grosse-Wentrup, M., & Bischl, B. (2021). General pitfalls of model-agnostic interpretation methods for machine learning models. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2007.04131*. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2007.04131>
- Mukherjee, P., Godse, M., & Chakraborty, B. (2024). Detection of autism spectrum disorder (asd) symptoms using lstm model. *WSEAS Transactions on Biology and Biomedicine*, *21*, 40–54. <https://doi.org/10.37394/23208.2024.21.5>
- Nápoles, G., Jastrzębska, A., & Salgueiro, Y. (2021). Pattern classification with evolving long-term cognitive networks. *Information Sciences*, *546*, 1102–1114. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ins.2020.08.058>
- Okoye, C., Obialo-Ibeawuchi, C. M., Obajeun, O. A., Sarwar, S., Tawfik, C., Waleed, M. S., Wasim, A. U., Mohamoud, I., Afolayan, A. Y., & Mbaezue, R. N. (2023). Early diagnosis of autism spectrum disorder: A review and analysis of the risks and benefits. *Cureus*, *15*(8), e43226. <https://doi.org/10.7759/cureus.43226>
- Perochon, S., Di Martino, J. M., Carpenter, K. L. H., Compton, S., Davis, N., Eichner, B., Espinosa, S., Franz, L., Krishnappa Babu, P. R., Sapiro, G., & Dawson, G. (2023). Early detection of autism using digital behavioral phenotyping. *Nature Medicine*, *29*(10), 2489–2497. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41591-023-02574-3>
- Portillo, N. L., Thammathorn, L. P., Buitrago, L. M., Carter, A. S., Sheldrick, R. C., & Eisenhower, A. (2024). Disparities in receipt of early intervention services by toddlers with autism diagnoses: An intersectional latent class analysis of demographic factors [Online ahead of print]. *Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10803-024-06613-x>
- Senaviratna, N. A., & Cooray, T. M. (2019). Diagnosing multicollinearity of logistic regression model. *Asian Journal of Probability and Statistics*, *5*(2), 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.9734/ajpas/2019/v5i230132>

- Shaw, K. A., Williams, S., Patrick, M. E., et al. (2025). Prevalence and early identification of autism spectrum disorder among children aged 4 and 8 years — autism and developmental disabilities monitoring network, 16 sites, united states, 2022 [16-site Autism and Developmental Disabilities Monitoring Network]. *MMWR Surveillance Summaries*, 74(SS-2), 1–22. <https://doi.org/10.15585/mmwr.ss7402a1>
- Supekar, K., de Los Angeles, C., Ryali, S., Cao, K., Ma, T., & Menon, V. (2022). Deep learning identifies robust gender differences in functional brain organization and their dissociable links to clinical symptoms in autism. *The British Journal of Psychiatry*, 220, 202–209. <https://doi.org/10.1192/bjp.2022.13>
- Szwed, P. (2021). Classification and feature transformation with fuzzy cognitive maps. *Applied Soft Computing*, 105, 107271. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asoc.2021.107271>
- Tang, M., Kumar, P., Chen, H., & Shrivastava, A. (2020). Deep multimodal learning for the diagnosis of autism spectrum disorder. *Journal of Imaging*, 6(6), 47. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jimaging6060047>
- Thabtah, F. (2019). Machine learning in autistic spectrum disorder behavioral research: A review and ways forward. *Informatics for Health and Social Care*, 44(3), 278–297. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17538157.2017.1399132>
- Tonekaboni, S., Joshi, S., McCradden, M. D., & Goldenberg, A. (2019). What clinicians want: Contextualizing explainable machine learning for clinical end use. *npj Digital Medicine*, 2(1), 1–6.
- Turbé, H., Bjelogrić, M., Lovis, C., et al. (2023). Evaluation of post-hoc interpretability methods in time-series classification. *Nature Machine Intelligence*, 5, 250–260. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s42256-023-00620-w>
- Vellido, A. (2019). The importance of interpretability and visualization in machine learning for applications in medicine and health care. *Neural Computing and Applications*, 32, 18069–18083. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00521-019-04051-w>
- Vimbi, V., Shaffi, N., Sadiq, M. A. K., Sirasanagandla, S. R., Aradhya, V. N. M., Kaiser, M. S., Wang, S., & Mahmud, M. (2025). Application of explainable artificial intelligence in autism spectrum disorder detection. *Cognitive Computation*, 17(3). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12559-025-10462-w>
- Yang, G., Ye, Q., & Xia, J. (2022). Unbox the black-box for the medical explainable ai via multi-modal and multi-centre data fusion: A mini-review, two showcases and beyond. *Information Fusion*, 77, 29–52. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.inffus.2021.07.016>

- Yasodhara, A., Asgarian, A., Huang, D., & Sobhani, P. (2021). On the trustworthiness of tree ensemble explainability methods. In *Machine learning and knowledge extraction* (pp. 293–308). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-84060-0_19
- Zhang, S., Xiao, L., Huang, H., & Hu, Z. (2024). Attention-stacking adaptive fuzzy neural networks for autism diagnosis. *2024 IEEE International Conference on Bioinformatics and Biomedicine (BIBM)*, 5654–5661. <https://doi.org/10.1109/BIBM62325.2024.10822467>

15 APPENDIX

15.1 Additional Demographic and Clinical Plots

Figure 24: Gender distribution by ASD diagnosis. A female-skewed pattern is observed in the ASD group, which contrasts with typical ASD prevalence trends.

The female-majority ASD group diverges from epidemiological norms and may reflect dataset-specific sampling or biases introduced during synthetic data generation. This shift introduces the risk that models may disproportionately associate ASD traits with female patterns—necessitating subgroup fairness evaluation across gender.

Figure 25: Age distribution by diagnosis. A younger age profile is observed in the ASD group. Note that the dataset is predominantly White-European, limiting generalizability.

Figure 26: Ethnic composition by ASD diagnosis. While variation exists, the dataset is heavily skewed toward White-European participants.

Figure 27: Relationship of the respondent to the individual assessed. Most responses were self-reported or completed by a parent.

Figure 28: Prior use of the autism screening app. Most respondents reported no prior exposure, limiting potential familiarity bias.

Figure 29: Prevalence of neonatal jaundice by ASD diagnosis. Higher incidence is observed in the ASD group, reflecting potential perinatal risk factors.

Figure 30: Reported family history of autism by diagnosis. A pronounced difference between groups supports the known heritability of ASD.

The strong contrast in jaundice history and familial autism prevalence reflects known risk factors and contributes predictive value. However, their inclusion also raises ethical concerns about overreliance on proxy biological or familial indicators in diagnostic contexts.

Return to main text section on Exploratory Data Analysis

15.2 Model Hyperparameter Grids

Table 6: Hyperparameter grid used for model optimization.

Model	Tuned Hyperparameters
LR	Penalty: L2; $C \in [0.001, 100]$ (log scale); Solver: <i>saga</i>
RF	Estimators: {100, 200}; Max Depth: {5, 10, None}; Min Samples Split: {2, 5, 10}; Min Samples Leaf: {1, 2, 4}; Max Features: <i>sqrt/log2</i> ; Bootstrap: True/False
TabNet	$n_d, n_a \in \{8, 16\}$; Decision Steps $\in \{3, 5\}$; $\lambda_{\text{sparse}} \in \{10^{-3}, 10^{-4}\}$; $\gamma \in \{1.0, 1.3\}$
XGBoost	Max Depth: {2, 3, 4}; Estimators: {50, 100}; Learning Rate: {0.01, 0.05, 0.1}; Subsample: {0.7, 0.8, 0.9}; Gamma: {0, 0.1, 0.2}
LTCN	Reasoning Steps $T \in \{10, 15, 20, 25, 30, 35\}$; Memory Decay $\phi \in \{0.5, 0.8, 0.85, 0.9, 0.95\}$; Activation: <i>sigmoid, tanh</i> ; Optimization: <i>inverse, ridge</i> ; Regularization $\alpha \in \{10^{-4}, 10^{-3}, 10^{-2}\}$

[Return to main text section on hyperparameter optimization.](#)

15.2.1 Summary of Key Findings in the Literature

Table 7: ML Models for ASD Diagnosis.

Category	Models	Pros	Cons
Traditional ML	LR, DT, RF	Simple, interpretable	Overfitting, assumes linearity
Deep Learning	CNN, LSTM	Powerful, captures complexity	Resource-intensive, sensitive to input
Hybrid/Fuzzy	FCM, TSK	Balance of accuracy and clarity	Scalability and complexity issues
Attention-based	TabNet LSTM + Attention	Temporal modeling, built-in explanations	Mixed results, low generalizability
Multimodal	XGB + features	Higher accuracy via integration	Interpretation can be unstable
Explainability	SHAP, LIME	Common, useful post-hoc tools	Costly, sometimes unreliable
Real-world Use	SenseToKnow	Interpretable, high clinical value	Needs broader validation

Table 8: Summary of Selected ML Studies in ASD Diagnosis

Study	Dataset	Model(s)	Acc.	AUC	Interpretability Method	Notes
Duda et al. (2016)	SRS	LR, RF	92–96%	0.965	Feature Selection (MI)	LR needed fewer features than RF
Heinsfeld et al. (2018)	ABIDE (fMRI)	Au toen-coder	70%	–	–	Deep learning applied to neuroimaging
Tang et al. (2020)	ABIDE (MRI+ROI)	CNN	74%	–	–	F1=0.805; multi-modal architecture
Zhang et al. (2024)	ABIDE (rs-fMRI)	(rs- AT-STTSK	85.7%	–	Fuzzy Logic (in-model)	Hybrid fuzzy transformer model
Cheong et al. (2024)	Custom (genetics+behavior)	XGBoost	83.95%	–	SHAP	No validation of SHAP explanations
Mainas et al. (2024)	Neuroimaging	TabNet	<70%	<0.70	Native feature masking	Underperformed vs SVM
Perochon et al. (2023)	SenseToKnow App	Custom	–	0.90	SHAP	NPV 97.8%, good real-world utility

The tables highlight the heterogeneity in both dataset types and model performance in ASD diagnosis literature. While traditional models like LR show high accuracy with minimal features, deep learning and hybrid models often trade interpretability for slight gains in performance. Furthermore, although post-hoc interpretability tools such as SHAP are common, few studies validate their consistency or discuss computational limitations. This reinforces the need for more standardized, interpretable, and equitable ML pipelines in ASD screening.

Return on main text

15.3 Supplementary Evaluation Visuals with SMOTE

XGBoost and RF clearly outperform the others, achieving low false negative and false positive rates which is critical in ASD screening where missed diagnoses carry high clinical risk. LR, while simpler, maintains competitive performance with relatively balanced error rates, reinforcing its value in interpretable settings. LTCNs demonstrates moderate classification capability but struggles with class separability, as reflected in its flatter ROC curve. TabNet underperforms across all metrics, with high false

negatives and poor ROC area, indicating a lack of discriminatory power despite its architectural complexity.

Figure 31: The model displays moderate false positives (20) and low false negatives (5) which reflects a balanced performance. Its simple linear nature yields 103 correct 'No ASD' predictions and 32 correct 'ASD' identifications that illustrates its practical reliability despite lacking complexity.

Figure 32: With an AUC of 0.93, the model demonstrates excellent separability between classes demonstrate more complex classifiers. This supports its value as an interpretable and dependable baseline model.

Figure 33: With 16 false positives and 7 false negatives, this model exhibits reasonably balanced performance. LTCN demonstrates strong generalization capabilities which position it as an effective grey-box model.

Figure 34: The near-linear shape of the curve, despite an AUC of 0.84, reveals limited discriminative ability in ranking ASD versus non-ASD cases. This linearity suggests that the model struggles to prioritize true positives without also increasing false positives, which indicates potential drawbacks in threshold sensitivity and separability.

Figure 35: This model achieved one of the strongest performances, with only 10 false positives and 7 false negatives. The model successfully identifies 113 'No ASD' and 30 'ASD' instances, confirming its robust precision and recall.

Figure 36: With an AUC of 0.93, this classifier offers high discriminative power and stable behavior across thresholds—essential in minimizing diagnostic errors in sensitive clinical settings.

Figure 37: The model underperforms with 29 false negatives and only 8 correct ASD predictions, which makes it unsuitable for ASD detection due to its high miss rate and low recall.

Figure 38: The low AUC of 0.57 suggests the model struggles to separate ASD from non-ASD cases.

Figure 39: XGBoost shows outstanding performance with only 6 false negatives and 9 false positives, accurately classifying 114 'No ASD' and 31 'ASD' cases. This makes it highly dependable in diagnostic contexts.

Figure 40: Matching the RF in AUC (0.93), the model demonstrates superior class discrimination, suggesting a strong balance between sensitivity and specificity.

15.3.1 Best Hyperparameters with SMOTE

Table 9: Best Hyperparameters for Each Model

Model	Selected Hyperparameters
LR	Penalty: <i>l2</i> Solver: <i>saga</i>
RF	n_estimators: 100 max_depth: None min_samples_split: 10 min_samples_leaf: 2
XGBOOST	n_estimators: 100 max_depth: 4 learning_rate: 0.1 subsample: 0.9 gamma: 0.2
TabNet	n_d = 8, n_a = 16 n_steps = 5 gamma = 1.3 lambda_sparse = 0.001
LTCN	T = 25, phi = 0.85 method = <i>ridge</i> activation = <i>sigmoid</i> alpha = 0.0001

15.3.2 Precision–Recall Curves for Model Evaluation

Figure 41: The nearly linear descent illustrates declining precision with increasing recall, suggesting limited ability to manage sensitivity-specificity trade-offs.

Figure 42: The curve shows relatively high precision across moderate recall levels, demonstrating the model's balanced behavior and reliability despite its simplicity.

Figure 43: The model maintains high precision, especially at lower recall levels, and demonstrates strong trade-off handling across threshold settings.

Figure 44: The curve is irregular and generally low across both axes, indicating weak model calibration and sensitivity—consistent with its poor overall performance

Figure 45: The curve stays high in both precision and recall, confirming the model's strength in identifying ASD cases with minimal trade-off losses.

15.3.3 Positive Prediction Rate (PPR) with SMOTE

Table 10 presents the Positive Prediction Rates (PPR) for male and female individuals across the evaluated models. The disparity is calculated as the absolute difference between the male and female rates. Notably, despite the dataset containing a higher proportion of female instances, the models consistently exhibit higher PPR for male individuals.

Table 10: Positive Prediction Rates by Gender

Model	Male Rate (%)	Female Rate (%)	Disparity (%)
LR	40.40	22.50	17.90
RF	33.70	14.10	19.60
TabNet	21.30	4.20	17.10
XGBoost	33.70	14.10	19.60
LTCN	34.80	21.10	13.70

As observed, all models exhibit a measurable disparity in PPR between male and female subjects. The **RF** and **XGBoost** models show the highest gender disparity at 19.6% which reveals a potential bias in classification. The **TabNet** model is especially conservative for female subjects, predicting ASD positivity at only 4.2%, which is significantly lower than its male counterpart. Among all, the **LTCNs** model shows the **lowest** disparity (13.7%) that indicates a relatively more balanced behavior.

While the PPR provides a quick snapshot of potential bias by showing differences in positive predictions between genders, it can be misleading if looked at on its own. PPR doesn't consider how many of those predictions are actually correct or incorrect within each group, nor does it tell us how well the model truly identifies positive cases for males and females separately. For instance, a model might have similar PPRs for both genders but still perform much worse for one gender in terms of precision or recall, resulting in unfair treatment. That's why it's important to go beyond PPR and examine more detailed gender-specific measures like precision, recall, and F1-score. These metrics help uncover deeper imbalances in how accurately and consistently the model diagnoses each group, offering a clearer and fairer picture of performance across genders.

15.3.4 Gender Distribution

To assess gender-related fairness, we computed precision, recall, and F1-score separately for male and female individuals. As shown in , LR yields an F1-score of 0.774 for males and 0.593 for females, with recall dropping from 0.923 to 0.727—a notable **18% absolute decline** in sensitivity for female cases. RF performs better, with F1-scores of 0.821 (male) and 0.667 (female), though a **15.4% gap** persists. TabNet demonstrates the greatest imbalance: male recall is 0.269 and female recall just 0.091, resulting in very low F1-scores of 0.311 and 0.143, respectively. XGBoost achieves the most balanced performance, with F1-scores of 0.821 for males and 0.762 for females—the **smallest gap** (5.9%)—alongside high precision and recall for both groups. LTCNs scores 0.772 (male) and 0.615 (female), with a **15.7% disparity**, mainly due to reduced female precision (0.533). These trends, reflected in the confusion matrices, show that while XGBoost maintains diagnostic consistency across genders, models like TabNet and LR reveal substantial gender-related disparities, see Table 16.

Figure 46: Demonstrates strong performance with high recall (88.5%) and low false negatives (3). A few false positives remain (7), but the model appears well-calibrated for male ASD detection.

Figure 47: Recall drops to 63.6%, with 4 false negatives. The model still captures more ASD cases than some others such as TabNet, but sensitivity is clearly reduced compared to the male group.

Figure 48: The model struggles to detect ASD in males, achieving recall of only 26.9%. It misses the majority of ASD cases (19 false negatives), making it unreliable in this subgroup.

Figure 49: Performance is critically poor with only 1 true positive out of 11 ASD cases. The model fails to detect ASD in most female instances, which severely limits clinical usefulness and introduces significant bias.

Figure 50: The model achieves very high recall (92.3%), correctly identifying most ASD-positive males. However, it shows a moderate number of false positives (12), suggesting a tendency to over-predict ASD in non-ASD males.

Figure 51: The model identifies fewer ASD cases in females, leading to lower recall (72.7%) and a slightly higher rate of false positives (8). This indicates reduced sensitivity and precision compared to the male group.

Figure 52: High precision and recall (88.5%) result in strong overall performance, with low false negatives and balanced classification. The model effectively identifies ASD cases in males.

Figure 53: Nearly matches male performance with 72.7% recall and high precision (80%), demonstrating robust and equitable classification across genders.

Figure 54: Delivers high recall (84.6%) and a balanced trade-off between false positives (9) and false negatives (4). Performance is strong, but slightly less precise than XGBoost.

Figure 55: Recall is maintained at 72.7%, but precision drops to 53.3% due to an increased number of false positives (7). The model is more sensitive than TabNet but less precise, indicating possible over-prediction of ASD in females.

Return to main text section on model evaluation and metrics.

15.4 *Visual Diagnostics in the absence of SMOTE*

Table 11: Best Hyperparameters Without SMOTE

Model	Hyperparameters
LTCNs	T = 15 $\alpha = 0.01$ function = sigmoid method = ridge $\phi = 0.8$
LR	penalty = l2 solver = saga
RF	max_depth = None min_samples_leaf = 2 min_samples_split = 10 n_estimators = 100
TabNet	$\gamma = 1.3$ lambda_sparse = 0.001 n_a = 16 n_d = 8 n_steps = 5
XGBoost	$\gamma = 0$ learning_rate = 0.05 max_depth = 3 n_estimators = 50 subsample = 0.7

Return to Evaluation without SMOTE

Figures 56 to 65 show confusion matrices and ROC curves for all models. Tree-based classifiers such as RF and XGBoost exhibited superior performance, with steep ROC curves and low false negative rates, a crucial trait in clinical settings where missed ASD cases carry serious consequences. The dataset was nearly balanced (1% deviation), minimizing class imbalance effects. Although RF and LTCNs produced identical confusion matrices (116 true negatives, 23 true positives), their ROC curves diverged: RF achieved an AUC of 0.92, while LTCNs reached only 0.78, indicating RF's superior calibration and ranking ability. The near-linear ROC curve of LTCNs suggests poor class discrimination and a bias toward

the No-ASD class. LR also performed well with an AUC of 0.92, but without SMOTE, its false negatives rose from 5 to 11, emphasizing the importance of rebalancing. TabNet underperformed across all conditions, with persistently low sensitivity and weak ROC curves, suggesting limited capacity to learn effective boundaries—even with SMOTE.

Figure 56: Correctly predicted 112 No-ASD and 25 ASD cases that shows strong balanced performance across both classes.

Figure 57: Achieved an AUC of 0.92 which illustrates excellent class separation and predictive performance.

Figure 58: Accurately classified 116 No-ASD and 23 ASD instances, with low error rate and good generalization.

Figure 59: AUC of 0.92 confirms high discriminative power and robust classification behavior.

Figure 60: The model correctly classified 115 No-ASD and 25 ASD cases, demonstrating high precision and sensitivity, which is particularly important in minimizing false negatives in clinical diagnostics.

Figure 61: Achieved an AUC of 0.92, matching the top-performing models and indicating strong discriminative ability.

Figure 62: Correctly classified 116 No-ASD and 23 ASD cases, suggesting balanced performance across both classes.

Figure 63: The near-linear ROC curve and AUC of 0.78 suggest moderate classification performance. The shape indicates limited discriminative power, with a tendency to predict primarily the No-ASD class, possibly due to class imbalance.

Figure 64: The model identified only 8 out of 37 ASD cases, reflecting poor sensitivity and a high false negative rate. While performance on the No-ASD class remained strong, this imbalance indicates limited clinical applicability where accurate detection of ASD is critical.

Figure 65: TabNet's AUC of 0.57 suggests it is closing in on random performance, with limited ability to distinguish ASD from No-ASD cases.

Table 12: Test F1 Scores With and Without SMOTE

Model	Test F1 (SMOTE)	Test F1 (No SMOTE)
Logistic Regression	0.85	0.86
Random Forest	0.90	0.86
TabNet	0.70	0.70
XGBoost	0.91	0.87
LTCN	0.86	0.86

Table 13: Comparison of Kappa Scores With and Without SMOTE

Model	Test Kappa (SMOTE)	Test Kappa (No SMOTE)
Logistic Regression	0.62	0.59
Random Forest	0.71	0.60
TabNet	0.12	0.12
XGBoost	0.74	0.63
LTCN	0.63	0.60

Table 14: Train and Validation F1 Scores With and Without SMOTE

Model	Train F1 (SMOTE)	Train F1 (No SMOTE)	Val F1 (SMOTE)	Val F1 (No SMOTE)
Logistic Regression	0.86	0.89	0.85	0.86
Random Forest	0.94	0.92	0.87	0.86
TabNet	0.64	0.64	0.64	0.64
XGBoost	0.94	0.91	0.86	0.86
LTCN	0.90	0.90	0.84	0.87

Figure 66: LTCNs maintain very high precision at low recall but experiences a sharp decline as recall increases, indicating strong conservativeness and poor coverage of positive cases.

Figure 67: Logistic Regression shows a smooth decline in precision as recall increases, indicating stable and probabilistic scoring.

Figure 68: Random Forest retains relatively high precision across a wide recall range, reflecting robust performance and resilience to class imbalance.

Figure 69: XGBoost achieves consistently strong precision and recall values, indicating highly effective positive class identification.

Figure 70: The curve illustrates the trade-off between precision and recall across different classification thresholds. A steep decline in precision at low recall values may indicate the presence of class imbalance or model calibration issues.

The comparison reveals distinct strengths across the models. LTCN adopts a precision-oriented strategy, capturing high precision by being highly selective in its positive predictions, even at the cost of missing many true positives., which makes it suitable for applications where false positives are costly. LR offers a balanced and interpretable performance,

making it a solid baseline. RF generalizes well, maintaining higher precision across a broader range of recall. XGBoost delivers the most favorable trade-off, consistently achieving high precision and recall, and is likely the best choice when both accuracy and sensitivity are essential.

15.4.1 Positive Prediction Rate without SMOTE

To assess potential gender bias in the models, we examined the PPR—the percentage of individuals predicted as having ASD—for male and female groups, without applying SMOTE oversampling. Table 15 summarizes the PPRs and the absolute disparity between genders for each model.

Table 15: Positive Prediction Rates by Gender without SMOTE Balancing

Model	Male Rate (%)	Female Rate (%)	Disparity (%)
LR	29.20	14.10	15.10
RF	25.80	9.90	15.90
TabNet	21.30	4.20	17.10
XGBoost	28.10	11.30	16.80
LTCN	25.80	9.90	15.90

As shown in Table 15, all models exhibit considerable disparities in PPR between male and female individuals. The highest disparities are observed in the **TabNet** model (17.1%) and the **XGBoost** and **RF** models (16.8% and 15.9%, respectively). For instance, TabNet predicts ASD in only 4.2% of females, compared to 21.3% of males.

These findings suggest the models may be learning gender-skewed patterns, possibly due to imbalanced features or differences in ASD presentation. The consistent underrepresentation of positive predictions for females, with or without SMOTE, raises fairness concerns and reflects real-world risks like ASD underdiagnosis in females—already noted in clinical research.

In the original dataset, all models performed better in identifying ASD among male participants, as reflected in consistently higher recall scores. For example, in the LTCN model, male recall reached 0.692 versus 0.455 for females; in LR and XGBoost, male recall was 0.731 compared to 0.545 for females. These disparities indicate a higher model sensitivity to ASD features more commonly associated with male cases, suggesting both

class imbalance and feature bias. After applying SMOTE, recall improved for both genders—especially among females. In LTCN, female recall increased from 0.455 to 0.727, and in LR from 0.545 to 0.727. While this indicates that SMOTE enhanced detection in underrepresented female cases, it also reduced precision, particularly for females. This trade-off reflects a common pattern: improved sensitivity at the cost of increased false positives. Overall, SMOTE contributed to fairer, more balanced performance, though the degree of improvement varied by model. For a full breakdown of gender-specific metrics, see Table 16.

Table 16: Diagnostic performance (Precision, Recall, F1-score) by model and gender, with and without SMOTE (ASD class).

Model	Male - No SMOTE			Male - SMOTE			Female - No SMOTE / SMOTE		
	Precision	Recall	F1	Precision	Recall	F1	Precision (N/S)	Recall (N/S)	F1 (N/S)
LR	0.731	0.731	0.731	0.667	0.923	0.774	0.600 / 0.500	0.545 / 0.727	0.571 / 0.593
RF	0.739	0.654	0.694	0.767	0.885	0.821	0.667 / 0.700	0.545 / 0.636	0.600 / 0.667
TabNet	0.368	0.269	0.311	0.368	0.269	0.311	0.333 / 0.333	0.091 / 0.091	0.143 / 0.143
XGB	0.760	0.731	0.745	0.767	0.885	0.821	0.750 / 0.800	0.545 / 0.727	0.632 / 0.762
LTCN	0.783	0.692	0.735	0.710	0.846	0.772	0.714 / 0.533	0.455 / 0.727	0.556 / 0.615

Figure 71: The model correctly identified 18 out of 26 ASD cases (Recall = 0.692) and showed strong performance on No-ASD detection, achieving balanced classification.

Figure 72: The model correctly classified 58 No-ASD and 5 ASD cases, but missed 6 ASD instances, reflecting low sensitivity (Recall = 0.455).

Figure 73: Correctly classified 19 of 26 ASD cases with a recall of 0.731 and consistent performance across both classes.

Figure 74: Slightly improved recall (0.545) with 6 true ASD positives, though 5 were missed.

Figure 75: Achieved a recall of 0.654 on ASD detection (17 out of 26 correctly classified), maintaining strong precision across classes.

Figure 76: Correctly identified 6 out of 11 ASD cases with strong No-ASD classification, yielding moderate balance.

Figure 77: Correctly identified only 7 out of 26 ASD cases (Recall = 0.269), with a high number of false negatives, indicating poor clinical utility.

Figure 78: Only 1 ASD case correctly classified out of 11, indicating poor sensitivity and practical unreliability.

Figure 79: The model achieved a high recall of 0.731, accurately detecting 19 of 26 ASD cases and maintaining strong overall balance.

Figure 80: Achieved 6 true positives with a recall of 0.545 and good No-ASD classification, showing moderate group fairness.

Continue on feature importance section

16.1 Visual Inspection of Marginalization Curves

Figure 81: SHAP and SOFI outperform both the native and PFI methods by more effectively identifying impactful features in the early stages of marginalization.

Figure 82: SOFI yields the earliest performance loss, despite the inherently interpretable model structure.

Figure 83: Performance degradation under feature removal shows SOFI providing more efficient identification of sensitive features than the native or PFI.

Figure 84: The step initial decline in the SOFI-driven curve highlights the method’s ability to effectively identify and neutralize key features leveraged by TabNet’s attention mechanisms, with PFI and Native methods following in effectiveness.

Figure 85: SOFI rankings lead to the most pronounced early F1 decline, outperforming PFI, SHAP, and native methods. This suggests superior alignment with model sensitivities.

Return to the main text: [PMCs](#).

16.2 PMCs without SMOTE

Figure 86: SOFI shows the steepest curve, which indicates the strongest alignment with feature importance. PFI follows, while Native shows the least sensitivity to top-ranked features.

Figure 87: SOFI leads to the steepest drop that reveals the most accurate identification of influential features, followed by Native and then PFI.

Figure 88: SOFI shows the steepest degradation, followed by SHAP, PFI, and Native, indicating its superior ability to identify critical features.

Figure 89: SOFI shows the steepest overall curve, indicating the most accurate identification of critical features. While PFI briefly surpasses SOFI at certain point, SOFI maintains stronger performance across the full marginalization path. Native shows a more gradual decline which reflects lower alignment with feature relevance.

Figure 90: SOFI, PFI, and SHAP show similar performance degradation, with SOFI achieving the steepest overall decline which demonstrates superior feature ranking. Native shows the least sensitivity which suggests weaker alignment with model behavior.

Return to the main text: [PMCs Results](#).

16.3 Cross-Validation Performance Across Models

Figure 91: Per-fold F1 scores across 10-fold cross-validation for all classifiers. Models are distinguished using both color and marker/line styles to ensure visual clarity. LTCN and XGBoost exhibit consistently high performance, while TabNet lags behind, showing greater variability and lower F1 scores.

Figure 92: Per-fold weighted F1 scores for each model on the original (non-SMOTE) dataset. XGBoost and RF show consistently high performance across folds, while TabNet exhibits lower and more variable scores. LR and LTCNs demonstrate stable generalization with moderate accuracy, highlighting their robustness and interpretability.

16.4 Glossary of Terms

Key Definitions

Cohen's Kappa: A measure of agreement between raters for categorical data, adjusted for chance. Values range from -1 (complete disagreement) to 1 (perfect agreement); 0 indicates random agreement.

Gaussian Noise: Random variation drawn from a normal distribution, used to test model robustness under input imperfections or variability.

16.5 Robustness Evaluation under Gaussian Noise Injection

Robustness to noisy or imperfect data is a crucial attribute for machine learning models intended for real-world deployment, particularly in clinical settings where variability in feature measurement is common. To simulate such conditions, Gaussian noise was introduced into the training data, enabling an assessment of each model's ability to generalize under perturbations that reflect the inconsistencies often encountered in behavioral and biomedical data collection.

Table 17 presents the performance of four models—LR, RF, XGBoost, and LTCN—on training, testing, and validation sets after noise injection. TabNet was excluded from this evaluation due to its consistently lower performance in prior experiments both with and without SMOTE preprocessing, suggesting limited robustness under increasing data complexity.

To ensure a fair comparison, all models were evaluated using the same set of hyperparameters previously optimized on the clean training data. The only exception was LR, where we introduced an L2 regularization parameter (C) to enhance its generalization capacity. As a white-box model with limited expressive power, this adjustment was made to offer it a fairer footing when compared with more complex models.

Among the evaluated models, XGBoost showed the highest resilience to noise, achieving a test F1-score of 0.87 and a Kappa of 0.66, indicating strong agreement with ground truth under perturbed conditions. However, the gap between training (F1 = 1.00, Kappa = 0.99) and test performance suggests overfitting, which imply that the model may have learned dataset-specific patterns with limited generalizability. LTCNs demonstrated consistent validation , reflected by among the lowest Validation F1 standard deviation (0.037), which means stable generalization across cross-validation folds. However, this outcome can be misleading, as the precision-recall curve and ROC curve reflect a bias toward one class, even in the absence of noisy data.

RF also displayed robust behavior, with strong performance across both training (F1: 0.98) and test (F1: 0.86) sets, and a moderate validation standard deviation (Val F1: 0.83, Std. Dev: 0.048). Despite its simplicity, LR maintained solid generalization (Test F1: 0.85, Val F1: 0.81), though its lower Kappa (0.60) indicates reduced agreement with true labels—likely due to its linear assumptions and higher sensitivity to noise.

While these results offer useful insights, they provide only a partial view of each model’s performance. Further analysis—such as confusion matrices and ROC Curves—is essential to fully understand model behavior, especially in sensitive applications where the cost of false positives and negatives can vary significantly.

Table 17: Model performance under Gaussian noise injection (training data)

Model	Train F1	Train Kappa	Test F1	Test Kappa	Val F1	Val F1 Std. Dev.
LR	0.81	0.51	0.85	0.60	0.81	0.05
RF	0.98	0.94	0.86	0.62	0.83	0.05
XGBoost	1.00	0.99	0.87	0.66	0.82	0.04
LTCN	0.85	0.60	0.85	0.60	0.82	0.04

Return to Feature Importance analysis

16.6 SVD-Based Initialization and Uniform Feature Influence

LTCN Initialization via SVD:

To initialize the input transformation matrix \mathbf{W}_1 , Long-Term Cognitive Networks (LTCNs) use Singular Value Decomposition (SVD) to extract key structural components from the input data matrix \mathbf{X} . This decomposition is expressed as:

$$\mathbf{X} = \mathbf{U}\mathbf{\Sigma}\mathbf{V}^\top$$

- \mathbf{U} Left singular vectors (input space)
- $\mathbf{\Sigma}$ Diagonal matrix of singular values (importance of directions)
- \mathbf{V}^\top Right singular vectors (feature space basis)

LTCNs use \mathbf{V}^\top to initialize \mathbf{W}_1 , ensuring that the model attends to the dominant variance directions in the input space from the outset. This leads to more stable convergence during training and helps avoid poor initialization that might otherwise distort cognitive reasoning steps.

16.7 Python libraries and packages

Table 18: Overview of Python libraries and packages used

Library	Version	Purpose / Usage
<i>numpy</i>	2.0.2	Numerical computations and Gaussian noise generation
<i>pandas</i>	2.2.2	Data manipulation and preprocessing
<i>matplotlib</i>	3.10.0	Plotting and visualizations
<i>seaborn</i>	0.13.2	Statistical data visualization
<i>scikit-learn</i>	1.6.1	ML models and metrics
<i>scipy</i>	1.15.2	Numerical and statistical methods
<i>xgboost</i>	2.1.4	Gradient boosting machine model
<i>pytorch-tabnet</i>	4.1.0	Deep learning model for tabular data
<i>torch</i>	2.6.0+cu124	Backend for TabNet and deep learning tasks
<i>tensorflow.keras</i>	2.18.0	Keras utilities (e.g., <i>to_categorical</i>)
<i>imblearn</i>	0.13.0	Handling imbalanced data (SMOTE, pipelines)
<i>lime</i>	0.2.0.1	Local model-agnostic explanations
<i>shap</i>	0.47.2	SHAP value-based model explanations
<i>pygad</i>	3.4.0	Genetic algorithm optimization
<i>google.colab</i>	n/a	Environment and Google Drive mounting

17 AQ-10 ADULT AUTISM SPECTRUM QUOTIENT QUESTIONNAIRE

Question	Definitely Agree	Slightly Agree	Slightly Disagree	Definitely Disagree
1. I often notice small sounds when others do not.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. I usually concentrate more on the whole picture, rather than the small details.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. I find it easy to do more than one thing at once.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. If there is an interruption, I can switch back to what I was doing very quickly.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. I find it easy to 'read between the lines' when someone is talking to me.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6. I know how to tell if someone listening to me is getting bored.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
7. When I'm reading a story I find it difficult to work out the characters' intentions.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
8. I like to collect information about categories of things (e.g. types of car, bird, train, plant).	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
9. I find it easy to work out what someone is thinking or feeling just by looking at their face.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
10. I find it difficult to work out people's intentions.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>